

MULTIMODAL HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION IN ASSEMBLY

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Doctoral thesis

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Abstract

Human-robot collaboration (HRC) envisioned for factories of the future would require close physical collaboration between humans and robots in safe and shared working environments with enhanced efficiency and flexibility. The PhD study aims for multimodal human-robot collaboration in assembly. For this purpose, various modalities controlled by high-level human commands are adopted to facilitate multimodal robot control in assembly and to support efficient HRC. Voice commands, as a commonly used communication channel, are firstly considered and adopted to control robots. Also, hand gestures work as nonverbal commands that often accompany voice instructions, and are used for robot control, specifically for gripper control in robotic assembly. Algorithms are developed to train and identify the commands so that the voice and hand gesture instructions are associated with valid robot control commands at the controller level. A sensorless haptics modality is developed to allow human operators to haptically control robots without using any external sensors. Within such context, an accurate dynamic model of the robot (within both the pre-sliding and sliding regimes) and an adaptive admittance observer are combined for reliable haptic robot control. In parallel, brainwaves work as an emerging communication modality and are used for adaptive robot control during seamless assembly, especially in noisy environments with unreliable voice recognition or when an operator is occupied with other tasks and unable to make gestures. Deep learning is explored to develop a robust brainwave classification system for high-accuracy robot control, and the brainwaves act as macro commands to trigger pre-defined function blocks that in turn provide micro control for robots in collaborative assembly. Brainwaves offer multimodal support to HRC assembly, as an alternative to haptics, auditory and gesture commands. Next, a multimodal data-driven control approach to HRC assembly assisted by event-driven function blocks is explored to facilitate collaborative assembly and adaptive robot control. The proposed approaches and system design are analysed and validated through experiments of a partial car engine assembly. Finally, conclusions and future directions are given.

Keywords

Robotics, Assembly, Human-robot collaboration, Multimodal control, Function block

Sammanfattning

Samarbete mellan människa och robot (HRC) i framtidens fabriker kräver en nära fysisk samverkan mellan människor och robotar i säkra och delade arbetsmiljöer, för ökad effektivitet och flexibilitet. Doktorandstudien syftar till multimodalt samarbete mellan människa och robot vid montering. För detta ändamål används olika modaliteter som styrs av mänskliga kommandon på hög nivå för att stödja effektiv HRC och underlätta robotstyrning vid montering. Röstkommandon, som är en vanlig kommunikationskanal, används i första hand för att styra roboten. Handgester för icke-verbala kommandon åtföljer ofta röstinstruktioner och används för robotstyrning, speciellt för gripkontroll vid robotmontering. Algoritmer har utvecklats för att träna och identifiera kommandona så att röst- och handgestinstruktionerna associeras med giltiga robotkontrollkommandon på styrenhetsnivå. En sensorlös haptiskmodalitet har utvecklats för att tillåta mänskliga operatörer att haptiskt styra robotar utan att använda några externa sensorer. I ett sådant sammanhang kombineras en exakt dynamisk modell av roboten (inom både glid- och förglidningsregimer) och en adaptiv inträdesobservatör för tillförlitlig haptisk robotkontroll. Parallellt är hjärnvågor en framväxande kommunikationsmodalitet som används för adaptiv robotstyrning under sömlös montering, särskilt i bullriga miljöer med opålitlig röstigenkänning eller när en operatör är upptagen med andra uppgifter och inte kan göra gester. Maskininlärning, Deep learning, utforskas för att utveckla ett robust hjärnvågsklassificeringssystem för robotstyrning med hög noggrannhet, och hjärnvågorna fungerar som makrokommandon för att aktivera fördefinierade funktionsblock som i sin tur ger mikrokontroll för robotar i kollaborativ montering. Hjärnvågorna ger ett multimodalt stöd till HRC-montering, som ett alternativ till haptik, hörsel- och gestkommandon. Därefter utforskas en multimodal datadriven kontrollmetod för HRC-montering med hjälp av händelsestyrda funktionsblock för att underlätta samverkande montering och adaptiv robotstyrning. De föreslagna tillvägagångssätten och systemdesignen analyseras och valideras genom experiment på ett delmontage av en bilmotor. Slutligen presenteras slutsatser och framtida riktningar.

Nyckelord

Robotik, Montering, Människa-robotsamarbete, Multimodal styrning, Funktionsblock

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List of appended papers

Paper 1

S. Liu, L. Wang* and X. V. Wang, “Sensorless haptic control for human-robot collaborative assembly,” *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, Vol.32, pp.132–144, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirpj.2020.11.015>

Paper 2

S. Liu, L. Wang* and X. V. Wang, “Function block-based multimodal control for symbiotic human-robot collaborative assembly,” *Transactions of the ASME, Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, Vol.143, No.9, 091001, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4050187>

Paper 3

L. Wang*, S. Liu, C. Cooper, X. V. Wang and R. X. Gao, “Function block-based human-robot collaborative assembly driven by brainwaves,” *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, Vol.70, No.1, pp.5–8, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2021.04.091>—A video Presentation at 2021 CIRP General Assembly: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yZvANePpshc>

Paper 4

S. Liu, L. Wang* and X. V. Wang, “Sensorless force estimation for industrial robots using disturbance observer and neural learning of friction approximation,” *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, Vol.71, 102168, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2021.102168>

Paper 5

S. Liu, L. Wang* and X. V. Wang, “Multimodal data driven robot control for human-robot collaborative assembly,” *Transactions of the ASME, Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, Vol.144, No.5, 051012, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4053806>

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The papers 1–5 are listed here based on the time sequence of formal publication.

Other publications

Journal papers

Paper 6

Y. Zhang, S. Liu, Y. Liu, H. Yang, M. Li, D. Huisingh and L. Wang, “The ‘Internet of Things’ enabled real-time scheduling for remanufacturing of automobile engines,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol.185, pp.562–575, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.02.061>

Paper 7

S. Liu, Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, L. Wang and X. V. Wang, “An ‘Internet of Things’ enabled dynamic optimization method for smart vehicles and logistics tasks,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol.215, pp.806–820, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.254>

Paper 8

E. Flores-García, Y. Jeong, S. Liu, M. Wiktorsson and L. Wang, “Enabling industrial internet of things-based digital servitization in smart production logistics,” *International Journal of Production Research*, 2022. (Minor revision and Resubmitted)

Paper 9

Z. Guo, Y. Zhang, S. Liu, X. V. Wang and L. Wang, “Exploring self-organization and self-adaption for smart manufacturing complex networks,” *Frontiers of Engineering Management*, 2022. (Revision and Resubmitted)

Paper 10

S. Liu, X. V. Wang and L. Wang*, “Digital twin-enabled advance execution for human-robot collaborative assembly,” *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, Vol.71, No.1, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp>.

Conference papers

Paper 11

S. Liu, G. Zhang and L. Wang*, “IoT-enabled dynamic optimisation for sustainable reverse logistics,” *Procedia CIRP*, Vol.69, pp.662–667, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2017.11.088>

Paper 12

S. Liu, Y. Wang, X. V. Wang and L. Wang, “Energy-efficient trajectory planning for an industrial robot using a multi-objective optimisation approach,” *Procedia Manufacturing*, Vol.25, pp.517–525, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2018.06.122>

Paper 13

L. Wang*, S. Liu, H. Liu and X. V. Wang, “Overview of human-robot collaboration in manufacturing,” *Proceedings of 5th International Conference on the Industry 4.0 Model for Advanced Manufacturing*, pp.15–58, June 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-46212-3_2 (Keynote Paper)

Paper 14

S. Liu, L. Wang* and X. V. Wang, “Symbiotic human-robot collaboration: multimodal control using function blocks,” *Procedia CIRP of the 53rd Conference on Manufacturing Systems*, Vol.93, pp.1188–1193, July 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2020.03.022>

Paper 15

S. Liu, L. Wang*, X. V. Wang and M. Wiktorsson, “A Framework of data-driven dynamic optimisation for smart production logistics,” Proceedings of 2020 IFIP Conference on Advances in Production Management Systems, Part II, pp.213–221, September 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57997-5_25 (Best Paper Award)

Paper 16

S. Liu, L. Wang*, X. V. Wang and M. Wiktorsson, “Complex-network-based cyber-physical production systems subject to cascading failures,” Proceedings of the 9th Swedish Production Symposium, pp.395–406, October 2020. doi:10.3233/ATDE200177 (Best Paper Award)

Paper 17

S. Liu, L. Wang*, X. V. Wang, C. Cooper and Robert X. Gao, “Leveraging multimodal data for intuitive robot control towards human-robot collaborative assembly,” Procedia CIRP of the 54th Conference on Manufacturing Systems, Vol.104, pp.206–211, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2021.11.035>

Paper 18

E. Flores-García, Y. Jeong, M. Wiktorsson, S. Liu, L. Wang and G. Kim, “Digital Twin-based services for smart production logistics,” In2021 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC) December 2021, pp. 1–12. IEEE. doi:10.1109/WSC52266.2021.9715526

Paper 19

S. Yi, S. Liu, X. Xu, X. V. Wang, S. Yan and L. Wang*, “Vision-based digital twin for human-robot collaborative assembly,” the 55th CIRP Conference on Manufacturing Systems, Lugano, Switzerland, June-July 2022.

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Book Chapter

Paper 20

S. Liu, L. Wang* and X. V. Wang, “Sensorless haptic control for physical human - robot interaction”, pp 319–350, *Advanced Human-Robot Collaboration in Manufacturing*, L. Wang, XV Wang, J. Váncza, and Z. Kemény, Eds., Springer Nature, 2021. (ISBN 978-3-030-69177-6). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69178-3_13

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Nomenclature

AF	Assembly feature
AI	Artificial intelligence
ANN	Artificial neural network
BCI	Brain-computer interface
BFB	Basic FB
CFB	Composite FB
CNN	Convolutional neural network
cobot	Collaborative robot
DO	Digital output
DoF	Degree of freedom
ECC	Execution control chart
EEG	Electroencephalography
FB	Function block
GMS	Generalised Maxwell-slip
GNN	Graph neural network
GRU	Gated recurrent unit
HRC	Human-robot collaboration
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
LSTM	Long-short term memory

NOMENCLATURE

NN Neural network

RNN Recurrent neural network

SIFB Service interface FB

STFT Short-time Fourier transform

STGCN Spatial-temporal graph convolutional network

TCP Tool point centre

Chapter 1

Introduction

This dissertation studies multimodal human-robot collaboration (HRC) in assembly focusing on leveraging multimodal data for efficient HRC assembly driven by event-driven function blocks (FBs). This chapter starts with an introduction to the research background and motivation. Given the problem statement, the research questions and targets are summarised, and the adopted research methodologies are presented, followed by the thesis outline. Finally, the main research contributions of all the appended papers are drawn.

1.1 Research background and motivation

The Global Robotics Market was valued at 27.73 billion USD in 2020 and is expected to reach 74.1 billion USD by 2026, registering a compound annual growth rate of 17.45%, during the period of 2021–2026 [1]. Robots work as the key driver of competitiveness and flexibility in large scale manufacturing industries, especially in the automotive industry [2]. Robots have the capacity of speed, strength, accuracy and repeatability in heavy-duty task execution but lack the human’s flexibility and adaptability as well as high-level cognitive decision-making capabilities [3]. Therefore, the concept of HRC is proposed to integrate the skills of the robots with the ability of human intelligence and flexibility [4].

Robotic applications in factories of the future would require more physical collaborations between humans and robots in shared working environments where humans’ superiority in flexibility and adaptability are integrated with the repeatability and strength of robots [5]. Utilising robots as collaborative partners in the assembly lines has been actively explored [6]. For example, ABB and KUKA companies have already explored and provided HRC solutions to the production of the future. A collaborative

Figure 1.1: A futuristic vision of multimodal HRC in assembly

assembly solution of humans and robots is considered a promising solution in handling complex assembly processes as compared to robotic assembly with full automation. The ABB YuMi[®] robot and KUKA LBR iiwa[®] robot work as collaborative robots (cobots) and are designed to work alongside humans in close proximity. Cobots are often equipped with sensors that allow them to see and feel for intuitive control [7]. In particular, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the significant increase in the adoption of cobots for automation in the medical sector is performed [8]. However, heavy-duty industries prefer to deploy traditional industrial robots for automating their manufacturing operations owing to the payload and speed limitations of cobots [9][10]. Conventional industrial robots often do not equip built-in torque and/or force sensors [11], and most of today's HRC solutions rely on extra hardware/assistive systems such as force sensors for the monitoring of interaction force [12]. Therefore, a sensorless haptics approach can be considered as a promising tool to facilitate HRC in assembly without using any force and/or torque sensors. In addition, today's robots are often controlled by rigid native programmes that can no longer support efficient HRC [13]. To address such a challenge, multimodal robot programming offers an opportunity for intuitive robot control with less effort on conventional robot programming [3]. Within the context, human instructions (voice, gesture, haptics, brainwave, etc.) collected from a multi-sensor perception system can be used as multimodal triggering signals to robot control in assem-

bly, where the multimodal signals are trained and associated with valid robot control commands. However, multimodal data-driven robot control is challenged by the following factors: 1) accurate command classification approaches; 2) robust multimodal command fusion, invocation and execution; 3) precise trigger of control modalities. In parallel, the European Commission released a new industrial target of Industry 5.0 in January 2021 [14], and aims for a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry. It well matches with the core of the HRC, and also motivates the wide potential applications of HRC with the consideration of the human roles, compared with fully automatic robotic manufacturing. Therefore, the thesis is motivated by the problems of multimodal HRC for human-centric assembly. A futuristic vision of multimodal HRC in assembly is depicted in Figure 1.1.

1.2 Scope and research context

This work aims at answering research questions that are faced by multimodal HRC in assembly and offering multimodal support to HRC assembly. Multimodality means the use of diverse communication channels between humans and robots at the same time, and it is composed of gesture, vision, auditory, and brainwave commands. The multimodal HRC is the main result presented in this thesis, together with multimodal command classification systems for low-latency and high-accuracy robot control and assembly applications presented in each appended paper.

The applications are mainly focused on HRC assembly that is facilitated by verbal and nonverbal commands-driven control approaches, a sensorless haptic control approach, and a brainwave-driven macro-micro control approach. The HRC assembly includes 1) assembly feature (AF)-based assembly planning; 2) multimodal robot control; 3) FB networks used for algorithm encapsulation, invocation, and control execution; and 4) collaborative assembly execution and control by robots and humans. In addition, the multimodal HRC in assembly relies on 1) dynamic modelling of the robot, accurate contact force estimation, and admittance control for flexible robot manipulation in assembly; 2) convolutional neural network (CNN)-based voice recognition and long-short term memory (LSTM)-based hand gesture classification, event-driven FB networks with the fusion of the control modalities, multimodal intuitive control of the robot and collaborative assembly; 3) a deep learning-based brainwave classification system, an FB network for assembly planning and robot control, and macro-micro control to HRC assembly; 4) A programming-free multimodal interface, multimodal command fusion, control and execution, and multimodal data-driven robot control in assembly.

1.3 Research objective and questions

Given the discussions above, the main objective of the thesis can be formulated as:

To realise a multimodal HRC system in assembly with enhanced efficiency and flexibility.

Figure 1.2: Links between research questions and their association with appended papers

The thesis aims for using multimodal data to facilitate efficient HRC in assembly. The associated research questions (RQs) are formulated as follows:

RQ1: how to leverage verbal and nonverbal commands (voice and gestures) for intuitive robot control during collaborative assembly, specifically for robot motion and gripper control?

RQ2: how to use brainwave signals to directly control robots during the collaborative assembly in a constraint yet dynamic environment?

RQ3: how to develop a sensorless haptic approach for adaptive industrial robot control and efficient HRC assembly without using any external sensors?

RQ4: how to develop a multimodal control approach to facilitate adaptive robot control and reliable collaborative assembly?

Figure 1.2 shows the link between RQs and their association with appended papers. RQ1 and RQ2 discuss the use of verbal and nonverbal commands (voice and gestures), and brainwave instructions for intuitive robot control in assembly, respectively; RQ3 explores contact-based haptic robot control without using any sensors. The three RQs illustrate control modalities driven by four types of commands, respectively. Then, RQ4 discusses the fusion of multimodal commands and leveraging them for robot control in assembly. The first three questions are the fundamental for RQ4. RQ1 is answered by Papers 2 and 5. RQ2 is answered by Papers 3 and 5. Papers 1 and 4 address the answers to RQ3, and RQ4 is answered by Paper 5.

1.4 Research methodology

Scientific and standard research methods are adopted in this dissertation. It starts with the state-of-the-art and comprehensive literature survey with a focus on the multimodal HRC, followed by the method/experiment design and development targeting the research questions. This is facilitated by the related theoretical knowledge of modelling, simulation, control, and case validation. For example, a deep learning-driven brainwave classification system is developed for low-latency and high-accuracy robot control. Quantitative and qualitative assessments of experimental results are performed to validate the findings and conclude the research work. Using these methodologies, novel and specific contributions to multimodal HRC in the assembly are respectively developed in Chapters 3, 4, and 5 and each control modality is associated with the corresponding multimodal commands. Chapter 6 leverages all the multimodal data for safe and productive HRC assembly. In addition, applications in HRC assembly is governed by a combination of research approaches, availability of experimental equipment and assembly settings, and requirements on ongoing research projects.

Chapter	Title	Content	Relation
Chapter 1	Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background • RQs • Methodology • Contributions 	
Chapter 2	Related work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HRC & Assembly • Key enabling technologies • Multimodal control 	
Chapter 3	Voice and gesture-based control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers 2 & 5
Chapter 4	Brainwave-driven HRC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers 3 & 5
Chapter 5	Sensorless haptic control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers 1 & 4
Chapter 6	Multimodal robot control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paper 5
Chapter 7	Discussion and future work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussions • Responses to RQs • Future work 	
Chapter 8	Conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conclusions 	

Figure 1.3: Thesis outline

1.5 Thesis outline and relation to the appended papers

The outline of the thesis composed of 8 Chapters is shown in Figure 1.3, and the relation of each chapter with the appended papers is discussed. The thesis starts with Introduction (Chapter 1) with a research background, questions, and contributions. Chapter 2 summarises the related work including HRC and assembly, multimodal robot control, and key enabling technologies to HRC. Chapter 3 presents a verbal and gesture-based approach to HRC assembly, originally proposed as parts of Paper 2, together with a brief discussion of a case application in Paper 5. Chapter 4 presents a brainwave-driven micro-macro approach to HRC in assembly, which is the main contribution of Paper 3. Chapter 5 introduces a sensorless haptic control approach to facilitate HRC assembly, which is associated with the main content of Paper 1 and partial contributions of Paper 4. Chapter 6 depicts a multimodal control approach to facilitate HRC assembly, which is related to the main content of Papers 2 and 5. Chapter 7 summarises the thesis and highlight the future work. Chapter 8 draws conclusions.

1.6 Research contributions

In this section, the summaries of the contributions for all appended papers are given.

1.6. RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

Paper 1: A sensorless haptic approach to HRC assembly without using extra force/torque sensors is proposed for robot control and collaborative assembly. Accurate estimation of the external forces/torques enabled by precise dynamic models of the robot is realised, where the friction model within both the presliding and sliding regimes is also explored. An adaptive admittance control scheme is developed for accurate and flexible robot control and to support efficient HRC assembly. The effectiveness of the developed approach is experimentally evaluated and validated by a case study of a partial car engine assembly.

Paper 2: A novel FB-based multimodal intuitive control approach is proposed to facilitate HRC in assembly. Multimodal communication channels between a human operator and robots are adopted to collect sensorless haptics, gesture and voice instructions in a safe workspace. A novel multimodal approach driven by FBs is proposed to use multimodal commands for intuitive robot control and accurate collaborative assembly. Within the context, FBs work as an enabler to the fusion of multimodal human commands and are used for the encapsulation, invocation, and execution of the control algorithms during assembly operations. A case study in an assembly work cell validates the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Paper 3: A novel brainwave-driven control approach to HRC assembly enabled by FBs is presented. A brainwave classification system driven by deep learning is developed for low-latency and high-accuracy robot control. Stimulus-free EEG signals are used as macro control commands to the AF-based FBs that in turn offer micro robot control in collaborative assembly. A case study of a partial engine car within a collaborative assembly is performed to validate the developed system. This work offers multimodal support to HRC assembly, as an alternative to haptics, auditory and gesture commands. In this paper, the author is mainly responsible for literature survey, methodologies, data acquisition and analysis, experimental validation and paper writing.

Paper 4: A novel sensorless-based approach is developed to estimate the unknown contact force induced by the physical interaction between robots and humans. The model-based identification scheme is initially used to obtain dynamic parameters. Then, neural learning of friction approximation is designed to enhance estimation performance for robotic systems subject with the model uncertainty. The external force exerted on the robot is formulated as the external disturbance and estimated by a disturbance observer. A disturbance Kalman filter-based approach combining the momentum and the disturbance observer is developed to estimate the contact force under the compensation of the parametric and model uncertainties. The proposed approach is verified by a set of test cases on a heavy-duty industrial robot with 6 degrees of freedom (DoF), of which results validate

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the efficiency of the proposed approach to estimating the interaction force with high accuracy.

Paper 5: A novel multimodal robot control approach to HRC assembly leveraging multimodal data and event-driven FBs is proposed. An FB-based multimodal interface is designed to fuse high-level multimodal commands from a multi-sensor perception system, and accurately trigger defined robot control modalities. A deep learning-based classification system is for accurate and reliable translation of multimodal commands. Then, a multimodal control approach is adopted to facilitate human operators to intuitively control and work in parallel with the robots. Finally, a case study of a partial car engine assembly is deployed to a robot team to evaluate the developed system.

Chapter 2

Related work

This chapter covers an overview of multimodal HRC in assembly. This chapter starts with the definition, classification, and bottlenecks of current HRC research, followed by the applications of HRC, especially in assembly. A comprehensive study of multimodal robot control is presented in Section 2.2, and key enabling technologies to support HRC in the assembly are discussed in Section 2.3.

2.1 Human-robot collaboration and assembly

This section presents the definition, categories, and progress of HRC, as well as the HRC applications in industry, especially for production engineering.

Robots are good in accuracy, high strength and speed, and humans have a high level of flexibility and adaptability, and cognitive capability. HRC is to combine human capabilities with the efficiency and precision of robots [3]. Within such a collaborative setting, robots can support and relieve human operators, facilitate versatile collaborative operations and enhance productivity [15]. Automatic assembly relies on the high effort of conventional robot programming and precise information of assembly tasks. Assembly operations are often implemented in a workspace with fencing safety [16]. Within such context, robotic workstations are only able to handle specific tasks and have a high automation level, and humans are not allowed to enter the workspace of the robots for safety concerns. However, it cannot satisfy the demands of flexible and adaptive operations [17]. Current factories, especially in the automotive industry, often adopt robotic assembly on fixed production and assembly lines within the context of Industry 4.0, which aims for high automation and reliability [17]. In contrast, humans have the capability of flexibility, adaptability and decision-making during purely manual assembly, but are also challenged by the heavy-duty compo-

CHAPTER 2. RELATED WORK

ment assembly [18][19]. In January 2021, the European Commission released its Policy Brief on “Industry 5.0 – towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry”, and the shift of focus from technology-driven progress to a thoroughly human-centric approach that characterises Industry 5.0 is emphasised [2]. For this purpose, human workers would be closely involved in the design and deployment of new industrial technologies, including robotics and artificial intelligence (AI) [20]. Therefore, HRC envisioned for future factories would require safe and physical collaboration between humans and robots in close proximity for enhanced flexibility and adaptability [21].

Using HRC can facilitate better performance on product quality and overall productivity, and subsequently, numerous research efforts on HRC have been performed [3][22]. Various interaction scenarios define a varying degree of proximity for humans and robots. They can be categorised as ‘*co-existence*’, ‘*cooperation*’, and ‘*collaboration*’ [23]. ‘*Coexistence*’ represents working independently on different tasks in adjacent workspaces without safety fencing, but not in a shared workspace. ‘*Cooperation*’ defines the same workspace where humans and robots work alternately on different tasks within a process, but no direct interaction. ‘*Collaboration*’ means that humans and robots simultaneously work on the same tasks in a shared workspace. The benefits of HRC are summarised as follows: 1) higher productivity and product quality; 2) maximum flexibility and adaptability as well as high cognition capability; 3) eased human workload in a collaborative setting [3][4][24].

In recent years, research on HRC has been under the spotlight. Varying approaches to empower HRC in adaptive robot control, multimodal collaborative operations, dynamic assembly planning and safe interactions have been reported in the literature [25][26][27][28]. Motivated by the benefits of HRC, the use of HRC in production and manufacturing is considered a promising solution to meet the needs of efficiency and flexibility. The automotive industry is one of the most critical applications of HRC. For example, BMW AG signed an order of 5,000 KUKA robots deployed in new production lines and factories across the globe in 2020 [1]. In parallel, robot manufacturers are actively engaging the research of HRC not only on robots and system design but also on service solutions. For example, ABB and KUKA have invested in the study of HRC from robotic system design and reliable HRC solutions to facilitate industrial applications [29][30]. The ABB YuMi[®] system is designed to work alongside humans in close proximity, and also KUKA LBR iiwa[®] is introduced to develop efficient collaborative solutions to human-robot coexistence settings.

In the area of component assembly, the conventional automation approach has reached its bottleneck. What could be automated have been au-

tomated, leaving the rest to manual work by human operators [19]. Given HRC's advantages, utilising robots as collaborative partners to assist humans in production and assembly lines has been actively explored. For example, a comprehensive study of HRC in assembly is performed such as astronautic and automotive assembly [31]. Meanwhile, HRC assembly often involves a set of assembly operations from assembly planning and task allocation to task execution and robot actions [3]. A complex assembly can be decomposed into a set of assembly operations, each of which is associated and defined as assembly features (AFs) such as placing, insertion, and welding [27][31]. A combination of a set of AFs can be used to describe the plan of the assembly task, and also an assembly task is determined by the assembly logic that defines the assembly sequences of the task [32][33]. Therefore, varying approaches using AF-based assembly planning are developed to facilitate HRC assembly [34].

Safety in any HRC system is of paramount importance. Reliable and trusted safety solutions in robotic laboratories have been developed to facilitate safe HRC settings [35][36]. However, the safety concern remains the biggest bottleneck for the wide use of HRC in shopfloors of some factories [27][37]. In addition, for this purpose, strict and comprehensive standards and directives are developed. EU directives [38], indicative general standards and robot standards [7] are developed for the guarantee of the safety of the operation procedures. Considering the safety requirements for HRC, a new safety standard for HRC (ISO/TS 15066:2016) was released and it specifies safety requirements for collaborative industrial robot systems and the work environment [7]. Followed by the latest safety standard of ISO/TR 23482-1:2020, it describes methods that can be used to test personal care robots in terms of safety requirements defined in ISO 13482 [39]. Accordingly, safety strategies that mainly consider three types of robot safety have been explored, and they are defined as crash, active, and adaptive safety. The former two work for only 'safe'/controlled collisions, and timely detection of imminent collisions, respectively. The last is to intervene operations of the hardware equipment and then adopt actions [40].

2.2 Multimodal robot control

Customised or complex assembly operations often need to be completed with a high level of flexibility and adaptability in HRC assembly lines, compared with fully automated or purely manual assembly [41]. The latter either requires high efforts on robot programming under change of HRC environments or heavy manual labour. In addition, robots used today in HRC assembly are often controlled by pre-generated rigid codes, and conventional robot programming and the required expert knowledge for robot

(re)programming also remain a challenge to the wide use of HRC in the assembly field [3][42]. In parallel, the changes in the HRC environment may trigger the reprogramming and replanning of tasks during assembly [43]. To support efficient HRC, using human commands to facilitate intuitive robot control and efficient HRC assembly is actively motivated, because training courses of robot programming often are time-consuming.

In recent years, multimodal robot programming is considered a promising tool for intuitive robot control without specialised expert knowledge on robot programming [3][44]. In parallel, the advancement of sensor techniques has been used to embrace robotic/HRC systems with the ability of perception and cognition in manufacturing settings [45]. The perception modalities are often facilitated by the use of diverse sensors between humans and robots at the same time [46], and the complementary nature of different sensing modalities motivates the consideration of multimodal data fusion for enhanced efficiency in the advancement of HRC assembly [47].

As one of the most effective communication tools, voice commands are widely applied to facilitate robot intuitive programming and control [48][49]. The project MORPHA demonstrated the fundamental research results of using speech and touch instructions for robot control [50], and subsequent research activities in the field of intuitive control and programming for industrial and service robots [51][52]. In parallel, the use of both natural language understanding and gesture recognition as a communication channel is considered in a multimodal human-robot interface design, and then human operators can use both natural language and gestures to interact with a mobile robot [53]. Research results of the project SMERobot show the potential of the use of speech and gesture-based instructions in the intuitive programming of industrial robots [54]. Also, the combination of speech recognition with other control modalities such as haptic control is treated as an efficient means for intuitive interaction with collaborative robots, i.e. Universal and KUKA Robots [55]. The report of the EU project SYMBIOTIC demonstrates a symbiotic HRC system controlled by voice commands and gesture instructions in an assembly production setting where operators can intuitively work with industrial robots for the execution of assembly tasks [56].

The noisy background within the manufacturing context remains a big factor of limiting the use of the voice commands, in terms of recognition accuracy within online demonstration [57]. For this purpose, human gestures are explored to work as a nonverbal communication channel for intuitive programming and robot control [3][58]. Considering the gestures used in HRC, they can be classified as hand and arm gestures, head and facial gestures, and body gestures. A comprehensive study of gesture recognition is presented in [59]. Meanwhile, given the intention hidden in the gesture, the

gestures can be also divided into communicative and manipulative ones in terms of their characters [60]. The former can describe the communicative intention while the latter can be used for object manipulation such as translation, rotation, and deformation. Within the context of HRC, the communicative gestures are divided into symbols or actions that are commonly used for intuitive robot programming. The symbol gestures are labelled with linguistic functions by referential characters or modal functions, and action gestures depict the movement/action itself, which have been explored for human motion and action prediction combined with AI algorithms [61].

The voice and gesture commands are originally issued and controlled by human brains. This inspires the consideration of the use of brainwave signals for device control and manipulation [62]. For this purpose, brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) have been developed to collect the brainwave signals and allow human operators to interact with devices [63][64]. The potential of brain activities are measured as electroencephalography (EEG) signals through sensor headsets [13]. Therefore, the commercial development and applications of the devices used for BCIs have attracted attention, and varying sensor headsets embedded with different channels have been developed and used for human-machine/computer interaction [65][66]. A comprehensive study of performance analysis on a set of EEG sensor headsets is reported [67], which offers criteria for appropriate selection and use of the devices. EEG signals are often generated under external stimuli such as visual aids, where brain activities vary with the stimulus itself [68]. Varying approaches to facilitating the use of the EEG for robot control have been reported [69]. It often starts with EEG signal processing with background noise removal and feature extraction [70]. Time-domain and frequency-domain features are generated from raw or pre-processed time-domain EEG signals, and frequency transform of the raw EEG signals, respectively [70]. Time-frequency features are those calculated on the transformed EEG signals including time and frequency information [70]. The commonly used approach was to define the raw EEG signals and/or the transformed features as inputs but a deep learning system to recognise the patterns [71]. Research efforts on algorithms for EEG signal classification have been numerous, such as CNNs, recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and graph neural networks (GNNs), and their variants [5][72][73].

In addition, haptic instructions, as contact-based commands, offer multimodal support to HRC assembly, as an alternative to auditory, gesture and brainwave commands. Heavy-duty industrial robots often do not have the capacity of the force/torque feedback as mentioned in Chapter 1 [74]. To haptically control robots, a sensorless interaction approach is considered promising for this need and relies on accurate contact force estimation and adaptive robot control [75][76]. This promotes the investigation of the ap-

proaches of contact force estimation. They can be categorised into 1) the generalised momentum-based residual method with valid inertial parameters [77][78]; 2) disturbance-based force observers/estimators [79][80]; 3) current-to-motor signal-based force estimation methods [81]; 4) approaches driven by accurate inverse dynamic models of the robot with accurate base parameters identification [82][83]. However, these model-based approaches are impacted by the unmodelled effects and the parametric uncertainty [12]. Meanwhile, friction is critical to the performance of force-controlled mechanical systems [84]. Therefore, accurate friction modelling in both sliding and presliding regimes should be actively explored for good control of robotic systems [85]. The Leuven model is well known for its capability of accurately modelling the presliding and sliding parts of friction using a hysteresis function [86], but it is limited by the discontinuity during the transition states and the problem of stack overflow [87]. Also, the generalised Maxwell-slip (GMS) model demonstrates the success of estimating the friction behaviour in the presliding regime [88]. In addition, model-free approaches, such as neural network techniques (NN), have been used to identify the unknown nonlinearity and dynamics of the robotic systems [89][90]. For example, the nonlinear friction was approximated by using an NN-based observer [91][92], and the LSTM model was adopted to model the rolling friction where the hysteresis relationship between rolling friction and the motor angle is formulated [93]. After accurate estimation of contact force, force-controlled interactions are performed. For this purpose, admittance control has been widely used in applications of HRC, and it is to convert the contact force into reference position and velocities, and the adaptive adjustment of admittance parameters are deployed for better control performance [94][95].

2.3 Key enabling technologies to HRC

Multimodal fusion of the human commands remains a bottleneck in the symbiotic and multimodal HRC system [96]. Multimodal commands have different data formats and structures, and also simultaneous command inputs to the multimodal HRC system require not only a function of processing the signals in parallel or in series, but also accurate interpretation and translation of the commands [76]. The former considers the focus of interface design and data fusion [5][97], and the latter is associated with signal processing, classification, and identification as well as execution of the control modalities [98]. Therefore, a multimodal interface needs to be deployed to allow human operators to interact with robots/machines. However, data fusion of the multimodal command, accurate command classification, and switch of the control modalities remain a challenge in the multimodal interface design [76][99].

2.3. KEY ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES TO HRC

FBs, specified by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 61499 Standard [100], provide a component solution for distributed industrial automation systems and aim for offering applications with the capacity of portability, re-usability interoperability, and reconfiguration [101]. FBs are characterised by an explicit event-driven model with embedded algorithms and finite-state-machine-based execution control charts (ECCs) and have been widely applied for robot control and assembly [102][103]. Motivated by these capacities, FBs can be used for human-machine/robot interface design where algorithms for multimodal command processing are embedded for command identification and fusion [104]. The function of event trigger inside FBs is well suited with the features of HRC assembly driven by multimodal commands [5][105]. This makes it efficient for multimodal interface development and integration using FBs, and then each of the multimodal commands activates the defined FBs for control execution [106]. An FB is a functional module composed of FB interfaces, internal sequence and behaviours that offer data/event flow for triggering the execution of its functionalities and finite-state machine-based control [105]. The FBs can be categorised into three types, namely basic FBs (BFBs), composite FBs (CFBs), and service interface FBs (SIFBs) [107]. Within a BFB, the ECC can define a state machine and determine which algorithm is activated based on its state and the input events. A CFB consists of BFBs and/or other CFBs. An SIFB is used to communicate with devices and BFBs. With the context of the assembly, FBs have been successfully used for assembly planning and task allocation, dynamic process decision making, and execution of assembly tasks [105][108]. In these studies, the encapsulation and invocation of control and task algorithms, processing monitoring during task execution, and control of assembly jobs and equipment are facilitated by the use of the FB networks. A typical application instance demonstrates that an FB-driven robot control and assembly planning with enhanced flexibility and adaptability is developed for real-time decision making at the controller level for robotic assembly [33]. The tools used for FB development are summarised 1) 4Diac IDE: an extensible, IEC 61499 compliant engineering environment for distributed control applications [109][110]; 2) 4Diac FORTE: a small portable implementation of an IEC 61499 runtime environment targeting small embedded control devices, implemented in C++ [111]; 3) 4Diac FB library: contains FBs which are available on the 4Diac FORTE and can therefore be used to create IEC 61499 compliant control applications [112].

In addition, reliable HRC assembly in the factory shopfloors relies on accurate and robust extraction and translation of the multimodal commands [99]. AI, as an enabling technology, plays a key role in developing multimodal command classification systems with high accuracy [113]. For this

purpose, a brief summary of the machine learning algorithms on voice, gesture and brainwave classification is presented. In the deep learning era, the success of NNs on revealing image patterns makes them effective at the speech recognition task [71]. Various methods have been applied such as CNNs [114], RNNs [115], and recent Transformer networks [116]. RNNs as a class of NNs, specifically the extension of feedforward NN with the presence of loops in hidden layers, are naturally suited to perform the sequence analysis process as the RNN is designed to extract the contextual information by defining long-term and short-term dependencies between different time-steps of inputs. The LSTM [115][117], gated recurrent unit (GRU) [118] and RNN-Transducer [119] are commonly used variants of RNNs. The excellence of CNNs on image classification makes them effective at classifying images associated with speech commands, given their good generation and discrimination capability [114]. Some of the variants of CNNs such as residual CNN [120], deep CNN [114], and attention-based CNN [121] have been used for speech recognition. Recently, the Transformer Neural Network introduces a novel architecture of encoder and decoder blocks based on self-attention layers, and the self-attention that takes three inputs, queries, values and keys, considers different positions of a sequence and executes dependencies between inputs and outputs [116], and it also well performs in speech recognition. For gesture recognition, CNNs [114], RNNs [115], and artificial neural networks (ANNs) are popular methods used for gesture classification [122]. CNNs and RNNs have good performances for EEG signal classification in terms of accuracy. However, the spatial dependency between EEG signals is not considered [123]. EEG channels placed on the scalp generates non-structured data with a non-Euclidean space, a graph network can be used represent EEG channel connection over time. Therefore, research efforts on using GNNs for EEG classification have been actively explored, given its capacity on the analysis of graph data [124]. A comprehensive review of GNNs including recurrent GNNs, convolutional GNNs, graph auto-encoders, and spatial-temporal GNNs was presented in [125]. Combined with the application of FBs, the trained models using these algorithms can be adopted in the predefined FBs for multimodal command-driven robot control.

Robot manipulation during assembly can be controlled by a set of motion and gripper operations aiming for adjustment of orientation and position and gripper control. Therefore, the mechanism of command conversion from multimodal commands to robot control commands is critical [126]. For this purpose, the commonly used approaches rely on the model-based control and feedback data of robot controllers such as admittance and impedance-based compliant control. However, adaptive adjustment of motion parameters in the compliant control is not fully considered, and subsequently fine robot manipulation and high-accuracy assembly, especially for complex as-

2.3. KEY ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES TO HRC

sembly settings [127] cannot be achieved. An AF-based approach is adopted for HRC assembly [27]. With the context, the predefined AFs [128] can be used to associate with robot control commands, and a set of motion and control commands defined by the AFs are used to facilitate accurate assembly operations.

Chapter 3

Voice and gesture-driven HRC in assembly

The main contributions of this chapter are from Papers 2 and 5. The RQ1 in this thesis is answered in this chapter. This chapter proposes a verbal and gesture-based approach to HRC in assembly. It starts with the introduction of signal collection and translation of voice and gesture commands, followed by command conversion of valid robot commands. Finally, this is a section providing a general overview of the application.

3.1 Introduction

In recent years, approaches have been actively explored to facilitate intuitive robot control, especially in robotic assembly [3]. This is because today's robot control approaches are based on rigid native codes and thus cannot support efficient HRC. Meanwhile, large efforts on conventional robot programming are necessary for a dynamic environment of HRC. To address such challenges, intuitive robot programming provides programming-free approaches for robot programming without expert knowledge. Voice instructions, as a natural and efficient communication means, can be adopted as a human-machine interaction modality. For this purpose, this chapter uses a human voice to control the robot in an assembly setting. The robotic assembly needs many operations of gripper control, and this would trigger a large amount of robotic programming, especially under the change of assembly environment. To allow humans to work in parallel with robots, hand gestures, as a nonverbal/context-dependent communication channel, can be adopted to control robot grippers. The flexibility and efficiency during collaborative assembly can be in place.

Figure 3.1: CNN-based voice recognition

3.2 Deep CNN-based voice recognition

CNN performs well on revealing patterns underlying images, which makes them effective at classifying spectrograms associated with voice commands [114]. For this purpose, a deep CNN-based voice recognition scheme is presented as shown in Figure 3.1, and it starts with the conversion of the audio data into 2-D (dimensional) spectrograms in the frequency and time domains by short-time Fourier transformation. This is because the spectrum of the audio data is heavily relevant in both time and frequency information, and then using CNN for the extraction of the local pattern (relation) through weight sharing is feasible for reliable and robust voice recognition.

Then, the generated images are defined as the inputs of the deep CNN model. The CNN model includes convolution, max-pooling, dense and flatten operations, followed by a fully connected layer for outputs of the final results. In a convolution layer, the convolution operation is formulated as a function of the input map and feature map that is given by

$$y_j = f\left(\sum_{i \in S_j} K_{ij} x_i + b_j\right) \quad (3.1)$$

where K_{ij} is the convolution kernel of the i -th input map (x_i) and the j -th output feature map (x_j), b_j is the basis of the b_j -th feature map, and f is the ReLU activation function. In the convolution function, a filter is designed as a 3×3 image matrix that slides over the input map for production of a feature map, and 32 filters, 1 stride length, $177 \times 98 \times 1$ input shape are adopted in the convolution layer. Then, the maximum value of each of the

3.3. LEAP MOTION-BASED HAND GESTURE RECOGNITION

Figure 3.2: (a) Leap Motion sensor-based hand gesture collection and (b) LSTM model used for training hand gestures

local neighbour is calculated by using the max-pooling operations with a 3×3 feature map and 2×2 strides. The fully connected layer is used to output the classification results of the input images where the softmax function with six types of classes is adopted, and the value of the dropout parameter is 0.2. Then, the loss function in the training model is the categorical cross-entropy. The training dataset for speech recognition is created by AIY and TensorFlow teams [129]. The dataset includes a set of 105,829 one-second audio files with 30 words. Given the motion control in Cartesian space, six types of voice commands are selected, and they are ‘Left’, ‘Right’, ‘Up’, ‘Down’, ‘Forward’, and ‘Backward’, and the total number of the selected audio files used for training are 18,440. Finally, the classified results of the voice dataset are output, and the classification accuracy of the test dataset is 92.47%.

3.3 Leap Motion-based hand gesture recognition

In a natural HRC environment, speech signals are typically accompanied by communicative gestures. Hand gestures as a form of the nonverbal communication channel are used for robot control together with speech commands [58]. Hand gesture-based robot gripper control can be used to empower the efficiency of the robotic assembly. This chapter uses the Leap Motion[®] sensor to collect data of the hand gesture and motion, which are used for real-time representation of human hands. In the coordinate system of the

Figure 3.3: Hand gestures used for LSTM

Leap Motion sensor as shown in Figure 3.2(a), the hand gesture is depicted by three components in the 3D space, and they are the position of fingertip \mathbf{F}_i and the palm centre \mathbf{P}_i , and the hand orientation that is indicated by the components parallel with the finger (P_iO) and perpendicular to the palm plane (\mathbf{n}), respectively. Then, a set of feature vectors composed of the distance, angle, and height of the fingertips are generated from the data produced by the sensor and serve as the input of an LSTM-based training model for gesture classification.

The distance feature \mathbf{D}_i of fingertip i is formulated as

$$\mathbf{D}_i = \|\mathbf{F}_i - \mathbf{P}_i\| / \max_{i \in n} \|\mathbf{F}_i - \mathbf{P}_i\| \quad (3.2)$$

where \mathbf{D}_i is normalised in the interval $[0,1]$. Then, the angle feature \mathbf{A}_i of fingertip i is

$$\mathbf{A}_i = (\langle \mathbf{P}_i\mathbf{F}_i, \mathbf{P}_i\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i \rangle, \mathbf{O}) \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_i\mathbf{F}_i$ and $\mathbf{P}_i\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i$ are the vectors of the palm centre and the fingertip, and the projection of the fingertip on the palm plane, respectively, and \mathbf{O} is the palm orientation. The height feature \mathbf{H}_i of fingertip i is

$$\mathbf{H}_i = \|\mathbf{P}_i\mathbf{F}_i * \mathbf{n}\| \quad (3.4)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the normal vector of the palm plane. Then, the feature vector $\mathbf{V} = [\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{H}]$ can depict the state of the fingers. To perform online hand gesture recognition and control, a dataset that contains 8 types of hand gestures is acquired from 15 participants, as shown in Figure 3.3. Each gesture is recorded 10 times for a total of 1,200 data samples.

The success of the LSTM on handling time-based sequence make effective approaches on processing hand gestures [115], as shown in Figure 3.2(b). At a time t , an LSTM unit that is treated as a memory cell contains an input gate i_t , an output gate o_t , and a forget gate f_t .

$$i_t = \sigma(W_{ia}a_{t-1} + W_{ix}x_t + W_{ic}c_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (3.5)$$

3.3. LEAP MOTION-BASED HAND GESTURE RECOGNITION

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{fa}a_{t-1} + W_{fx}x_t + W_{fc}c_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_{ca}a_{t-1} + W_{cx}x_t + b_c) \quad (3.7)$$

$$c_t = i_t \odot \tilde{c}_t + f_t \odot c_{t-1} \quad (3.8)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_{oa}a_{t-1} + W_{ox}x_t + W_{oc}c_t + b_o) \quad (3.9)$$

$$a_t = a_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \quad (3.10)$$

where σ is the sigmoid function, W and b are the weight and bias vectors, respectively, \odot is the Hadamard product, and the final state a_t is controlled by o_t . Through adjusting the gates, long-time information can be realised, reserved, and updated. In the LSTM model, the input and output sizes of the LSTM unit with 1 stride length are 30 and 32, respectively, and the fully connected layer with a softmax activation function outputs a vector with a 6-D output size. The accuracy of the testing dataset is 95.83%.

To facilitate the robot control in the assembly, the voice and hand gesture commands can be translated into a set of valid robot control commands. FBs have been widely used for the robot control system. As shown in Figure 3.4, a BFB (left) and a CFB (right) with data/event input/output and internal behaviour are depicted. Within the BFB, the ECC is a finite state machine used for state transition, algorithm execution, and control outputs.

Figure 3.4: Structure of FBs (basic: left; and composite: right)

Here, FB networks composed of a set of BFBs are defined to use voice and hand gestures for robot control. As shown in Fig 3.5, an FB network of voice-based robot control is developed to convert the voice commands into valid robot control commands, where robot movement along a given direction through a set of labelled voice commands can be achieved. The workflow of the FB network starts with the collection of the audio signals using an SIFB *DeviceUnit*. *STFT* (BFB) is used for processing the audio file into frequency spectrograms that are defined as the input to the training model. Triggered by the input event *EI_CNN*, the *TrainedVoiceCNN* with the trained model is activated to classify the commands where the detailed training parameters and algorithms are introduced in Section 3.2, and the results of the classified voice commands are sent out as the output of *Commands*. To control the movement of the robot, a BFB of *MotionControl* converts the human instructions into robot motion control commands. Considering the robot movement in the Cartesian space, six types of the speech commands are adopted to define the motion control, and ‘*Forward*’, ‘*Left*’, and ‘*Up*’ define the robot motion along positive X, Y, and Z axes of the robotic world frame, respectively, and ‘*Backward*’, ‘*Right*’, and ‘*Down*’ are along with the opposite directions of the three axes, respectively. The motion control parameters can be adaptively adjusted by users. The identified motion control commands and parameters are sent out by data output variables *MotionCommands*, *Disp*, *Vel*, and *Acc* to an SIFB (*ControllerUnit*) for the execution of the commands. The *Disp*, *Vel*, and *Acc* contain the values of the displacement, velocity, and acceleration, respectively. The FB network of CNN-based voice control can perform the rough motion control of the robot in Cartesian space.

Figure 3.5: FB network for voice-based robot control

An FB network of hand gesture-based gripper control is shown in Figure 3.6. Initially, an SIFB (*GetDataFromLeapMotion*) works as a communication channel between-in and collect the data of the hand gestures from the Leap Motion sensor. The collected data are processed by the BFB *DataProcessing*, and the feature vectors of the hand gestures are extracted as the output of the *DistanceFeature*, *AngleFeature*, and *HeightFeature*, respectively. These features are fed into the trained LSTM model that is embedded in the *TrainedHandGestureLSTM* BFB. The detailed algorithms and training parameters are discussed in Section 3.3. When the arrival of the input event *EI_LSTM*, the *TrainedHandGestureLSTM* BFB is executed to classify the hand gestures and output the types of the gestures. Followed by the *Classifier* BFB, it transforms the identified gestures to the predefined labels as the output of *LabelofGesture*. The grippers are controlled by digital signals. Therefore, the *StateTransform* BFB generates the digital output (DO) signals that are defined as the output of *Open* and *Close* of the *ControlUnit* BFB, respectively, and finally executed by the robot controller.

Figure 3.6: FB network for hand gesture-based gripper control

3.4 Experiment and validation

The experimental results of using voice and hand gestures for robot control in assembly are presented in this section. Figure 3.7 shows the experimental setup connected with a robot controller, a Leap Motion sensor (\textcircled{L}) and a microphone sensor (\textcircled{M}) via Ethernet, a USB, and a wireless Bluetooth, respectively. The assembly scenario is to assemble a cylinder head (\textcircled{C}) of an engine block (3.4 kg) onto the engine block (\textcircled{E}), followed by securing

Figure 3.7: Experimental setup of FB-based voice-and-gesture-driven robot control in HRC assembly

components (\textcircled{S}) by human operators.

The assembly process, as shown in Figure 3.8, consists of 6 control steps driven by the FB network. The assembly task starts with voice command-controlled robot motion in Step $\textcircled{1}$ where the *Pick_AF_CFB* is executed to pick up the cylinder head. At the initial stage, the ABB robot is with the configuration of $(q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5, q_6)=(0.837337^\circ, -23.3201^\circ, 7.42173^\circ, -0.784974^\circ, 103.897^\circ, 101.234^\circ)$, and the position of the end-effector in Cartesian space is $(X, Y, Z)=(473.19, 5.64, 1224.84)$ (unit: mm). In Step $\textcircled{2}$, a set of voice commands are issued for robot motion control during collaborative assembly. After activated by the *Start_FB* for the start of the assembly, the voice commands of ‘*Left (L)*, ‘*Right (R)*, ‘*Up (U)*, ‘*Down (D)*, ‘*Forward (F)*, and ‘*Backward (B)*’ are converted into spectrograms using the *STFT* (short-time Fourier transform), and they are depicted by $\textcircled{1}$ – $\textcircled{6}$ in Figure 3.9(a), respectively. Mapping the voice commands with motion parameters in the world coordinate system is critical for reliable robot motion control, and the association relation of the motion control commands and voice instructions is formulated and shown in Figure 3.9(b). The robot motion control starts with the execution of the voice command of the ‘*Forward*’ in Step $\textcircled{2}$. Then, triggered by an *ELCNN* event, the *Trained-VoiceCNN* feeds the generated spectrograms into the training model for the command classification and identification. The *MotionControl* is activated by an *ELMCMD* event that is the identified command and then produces a set of motion control commands. Each of the commands contains a label

Figure 3.8: Assembly process of HRC assembly

of the voice command, a relative displacement (mm), a TCP (tool point centre) linear velocity (mm/s) for the robot, and the motion parameters are $[Voice, Disp, Vel]=[F, 285, 100]$. Finally, the robot control commands are executed at the robot controller for assembly operations through the *ControllerUnit* (SIFB). The experimental results show that the responding time of the voice-based motion control from issuing a command to the robot action is lifted to a level of milliseconds on average. During the process, the voice-based motion paths and parameters are shown in Figure 3.9(c), and adaptive motion control parameters composed of $Disp$ and Vel are adopted to quickly approach the assembly targets with a velocity of 100mm/s before accurate assembly operation at a low speed. Within the context, the paths ④ and ⑤ indicate the operation of picking up the cylinder head, and paths ⑩ – ⑫ represent accurately placing it onto the engine block by the robot at a velocity of 10mm/s.

After the execution of the voice commands, the state of the robot gripper is ‘closed’ as shown in the inset of Step ③ in Figure 3.8, and then the hand gesture commands are used for gripper control. The human operator poses a hand gesture above the Leap Motion sensor, and the collected raw data of the hand gesture are sent for the feature extraction through the SIFB. The generated feature vectors composed of $\mathbf{V} = [\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{H}]$ are fed into the *TrainedHandGestureLSTM* FB for the classification and identification of the hand gestures when triggered by the event *EILLSTM*, and the identified hand gestures as the output of the *Gesture* are then translated as the predefined gesture label. As shown in the top and bottom insets of Figure 3.10(a), the hand gestures are labelled by the text of ‘HG TEN’ and ‘HG SIX’ that are used to open and close the gripper, respectively. Then, the gesture labels are converted into a state variable using the *StateTransform*, and it gives the value for the DO signals for the gripper control. The

results of the gripper control are shown in Figure 3.10(b). To control the gripper at the controller level, the DO channel of the ABB robot named (*DO_Close_Gripper*) is defined and used for receiving the signal of the gripper control. The value with 0 of *DO_Close_Gripper* opens the gripper, while 1 closes the gripper. The change of the state of the DO signals is shown in Figure 3.10(c). It is necessary to define specific DO signals for the various robotic systems. Then, Steps ④ – ⑥ invoke and execute the FB networks of voice-and hand gesture-based control modalities for the motion control and the ‘*Open*’ of the gripper, respectively. During this process, the robot is controlled to place the cylinder head onto the engine block through the execution of the FB networks. The experimental results show that the proposed approaches have good performances in HRC assembly with enhanced adaptability and flexibility and facilitate FB-driven programming-free robot control.

3.4. EXPERIMENT AND VALIDATION

Figure 3.9: Results of voice-based robot control in HRC assembly: (a) spectrogram generated by the human commands, (b) definition of voice command in the robot coordination system, and (c) motion paths and parameters

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Figure 3.10: (a) Hand gestures used for the gripper control enabled by the FB network, (b) Gripper control activated by the predefined hand gestures, and (c) DO signals for the gripper control

Chapter 4

Brainwave-driven HRC assembly

The main contributions to this chapter are Papers 3 and 5. This chapter introduces a macro-micro control approach to HRC assembly enabled by FBs and driven by brainwaves. In the context, micro control for robots in collaborative assembly is provided by the FBs that use brainwaves as macro control command inputs. This chapter starts with an introduction to a stimulus-free EEG signal acquisition approach that can circumvent limitations and constraints associated with stimulus-based EEG, followed by an FB-based HRC assembly approach. Then, a deep learning-driven brainwave classification system is developed for high-accuracy and low-latency robot control, and it is facilitated by using wavelet transform to extract the feature matrix as the input. Robust translation of brainwave commands to robot control commands is executed to support collaborative assembly. Finally, an experiment of a partial car engine assembly is used to demonstrate the performance of the developed system.

HRC envisioned for factories of the future would allow human operators to work with robots side by side in close proximity for enhanced efficiency. In today's factories, many production processes are already automated using robots. Human cognition, intelligence, flexibility, and adaptability ensure the smooth running and quality of production processes [19]. However, the rigid programme-based robot control approach used in today's factories cannot support efficient HRC. To release engineers from tedious conventional robot programming, research efforts on intuitive robot control have been numerous in recent years [3], and human brainwaves have shown promising advantages compared to haptic, voice and gesture commands [63][64]. These human instructions are originally issued and controlled by human brains but within various forms. Therefore, a research question is raised: why not use brainwave signals to directly control robots? Therefore, brain-robot interfaces are explored to allow humans to communicate and interact with robots through brain signals and also used for conversion of brain activities

as a form of electroencephalography (EEG) into robot control commands for task execution [65][66]. The external stimulus, such as motor imagery and visual aids, are commonly used to collect EEG signals where the change of the brain activities occurs due to the stimulus itself [71]. However, the stimulus-based EEG collection approach is challenging in the dynamic yet constrained HRC assembly due to the physical limitations of collaborative settings. Within brain robotics, robust and accurate translation of stimulus-free EEG signals is vital to reliable collaborative assembly on the factory shopfloors. During this process, it involves extraction and recognition of the brainwaves, decoding the neural activity, and translation of EEG signals to valid control commands that robots can understand for assembly operations.

To identify the signal pattern, many research efforts have been reported such as motor imagery, P300, and sleep stage classification [123]. The most obvious approach is to use the generated signal features as inputs and deep learning to train and recognise the patterns. Then, a communication pipeline between humans and an EEG sensor headset is adopted for interaction with the brainwaves and devices in a collaborative setting. However, uncertainty in the HRC environment during assembly such as task and/or environment change may trigger the high effort on reprogramming and re-planning of assembly tasks, and adaptive robot control through brainwaves remains a challenge and hinders the wide use of HRC in assembly. In addition, the brainwaves cannot be directly understood by the robot, and translation of brainwaves to commands for robot control and task execution is complicated at the machine/controller level. To address this challenge, FBs are depicted by an IEC 61499 standard and have been widely used to control distributed industrial systems and processes [103]. An event-driven FB is depicted by a functional module embedded with algorithm encapsulation, invocation and control execution, as well as adaptive robot control during robotic assembly can be facilitated by the use of FBs [104]. Within the HRC system, brainwaves can serve as a high-level command to trigger FB execution for robot control, and event-driven FBs with assembly and control algorithms serve as a bridge between robots and stimulus-free brainwaves to facilitate adaptive robot control in collaborative assembly.

4.1 Methodology of brainwave-driven HRC assembly

The methodology of this section includes system design, EEG signal collection, command processing and classification, and command conversion from brainwave to robot control commands.

4.1. METHODOLOGY OF BRAINWAVE-DRIVEN HRC ASSEMBLY

Figure 4.1: System architecture of brainwave-driven HRC assembly

The architecture of the developed system includes four modules for efficient and effective HRC assembly as shown in Figure 4.1, with the brainwaves serving as control input commands to the FBs that in turn provide micro commands for adaptive robot control and collaborative assembly. Module ❶ is for brainwave collection from an EEG sensor headset and segmenting the brainwaves of a *command phrase* with the removal of background noise into command words. Module ❷ uses wavelet transform to convert the brainwave into feature inputs for a spatial-temporal graph convolutional network (STGCN) for high-accuracy command classification. Module ❸ is an FB network that is embedded with control algorithms activated by the classified commands, and the assembly feature (AF)-based FBs are defined and used for collaborative assembly where brainwaves are converted into robot control commands. Module ❹ receives and executes the resultant micro commands for the robot control and execution of assembly tasks.

The EEG signal is a recording of the electrical activity of the brain from the scalp, and the brain activities at the enumerated locations on the scalp are measured as an electrical potential over time. The EEG signal is a mixture of underlying base frequencies, which can reflect functional brain states and cognitive activities over time. The frequency band is decomposed into conventional five sub-bands (Delta: 0.5–4 Hz, Theta: 4–7 Hz, Alpha: 7–13 Hz, Beta: 13–30 Hz, and Gamma: 30–100 Hz) [97]. An EEG sensor headset with 16 wet electrode channels, as shown in Figure 4.2(a), is used to collect the EEG signals using the g.HIsys system and they are saved as a 16-channel array of the signal over time with a sampling frequency of 250 Hz. The electrodes are placed on the scalp based on the 10–20 system, and

Figure 4.2: (a) Stimulus-free brainwave collection and (b) placement of wet electrodes

the reference electrode (REF) on the right earlobe and the ground electrode (GND) are used as recording references, as shown in Figure 4.2(b). During the recording of the EEG signals, a command phrase issued by the operator is composed of a *subject*, a *predicate*, and an *object*, respectively, such as “robot place block”, and the command words of each phrase indicate the executor, action, and parts to be acted on, respectively. The invoked electrical potential of the cerebral cortex is measured as the EEG signals. Meanwhile, the human operator follows a rhythmic thought pattern to facilitate the extraction of command words. Specifically, the *subject*, *predicate*, and *object* were thought for one, one, and two seconds, respectively, with a one-second pause in-between. The EEG signals are then filtered by an online band-pass and notch filters of 0.1–100 Hz and 48–52 Hz, respectively. The former is to collect signals within the interested frequency, and the latter is to eliminate electric noise.

The recorded EEG signals are often contaminated with different artefacts such as eye-blink, muscle activities, and environmental effects, and such noise mixed in the signals poses difficulties on signal analysis and pattern recognition [113]. For this purpose, varying approaches to facilitating signal analysis and feature extraction have been actively explored [70]. The commonly used approaches are to produce the features of the EEG signals in time, frequency, and time-frequency domains [70]. The former two are obtained from raw or pre-processed time-domain EEG signals and frequency transform of the raw EEG signals, respectively. Time-frequency features contain the time and frequency information based on the transformed EEG signals. The appropriate selection of the approach used for signal analysis

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is critical to the performance of feature extraction. Followed by a comprehensive study on the feature extraction and performance analysis discussed in [70], the capacity of wavelet transform in revealing characteristics underlying non-stationary signals has made it effective at extracting the signal features associated with the brainwave commands [130]. The wavelet transform of a signal $x(t)$ is formulated as

$$wt(s, \tau, x, \Psi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \Psi^* \left(\frac{t - \tau}{s} \right) d\tau : s \in \mathbb{R}^+, \tau \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4.1)$$

where wt is the wavelet coefficient. s and τ are the scaling and shifting parameters, respectively. Ψ and Ψ^* denote the base wavelet and its complex conjugate, respectively. The wavelet transform can extract signal features over the entire signal spectrum by adjusting s and τ . A set of commonly used base wavelets are adopted in the wavelet transform for the feature extraction, and they are the base wavelets of ‘*B-Spline*’, ‘*Bump*’, ‘*Gaussian*’, ‘*Harmonic*’, ‘*Morlet*’, ‘*Morse*’, and ‘*Shannon*’ [5][130]. Energy-to-Shannon entropy ratio of the EEG signals is measured as a criterion to select the most appropriate base wavelet. The energy content of a signal $x(t)$ derived from the wavelet coefficients and its energy content at a specific scaling parameter s are measured as 4.2 and 4.3, respectively.

$$E_{energy} = \int \int |wt(s, \tau)|^2 ds d\tau \quad (4.2)$$

$$E_{energy}(s) = \int |wt(s, \tau)|^2 d\tau \quad (4.3)$$

The EEG signals are a discrete signal over time, and the corresponding formula with N discrete samples are as follows

$$E_{energy} = \sum_s \sum_{\tau} |wt(s, \tau)|^2 \quad (4.4)$$

$$E_{energy}(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N |wt(s, \tau)|^2 \quad (4.5)$$

Then, the Shannon entropy of the signal, which describes the energy distribution of the wavelet coefficients, is formulated as

$$E_{entropy}(s) = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i / \log_2 p_i \quad (4.6)$$

where $p_i = |wt(s, \tau)|^2 / E_{energy}(s)$ is the energy probability distribution of the wavelet coefficients, and $\sum_{i=1}^N p_i = 1$. The energy-to-entropy ratio (R) is described as

$$R(s) = E_{energy}(s) / E_{entropy}(s) \quad (4.7)$$

The values of R represent the amount of relevant information extracted from the signal, and the appropriate selection of the base wavelets can be determined through maximising R of a set of base wavelets. 12,800 EEG signals of 16 channels and based on nine command-words listed in Table 4.1 are used to calculate the respective mean values \bar{R} of R . The values of \bar{R} for the ‘*B-Spline*’, ‘*Bump*’, ‘*Gaussian*’, ‘*Harmonic*’, ‘*Morse*’, ‘*Shannon*’ and ‘*Morlet*’ base wavelets are 80, 66, 73, 85, 130, 149 and 172, respectively. Therefore, the base wavelet of ‘*Morlet*’ is selected because its value of R is the highest among the candidates. For brevity, the cylinder head and fuel injector tube are represented by *cylinder* and *tube* in brainwave commands, respectively.

Table 4.1: Command sample of words and phrases used for STGCN training

Subjects	Predicates	Objects	Command phrases
Human	Assemble	Block	Human place block
Robot	Insert	Cylinder	Robot assemble block
	Pick	Tube	Robot insert tube
	Place		Robot place cylinder
			Robot pick cylinder

4.2 Brainwave classification system

4.2.1 Spatial-temporal graph convolutional network

This section uses the STGCN to acquire the spatial and temporal features of the EEG signals. Motivated by the graph theory, a sensor channel or an electrode cluster of the sensor headset, as shown in Figure 4.2(a), can be treated as a vertex of a graph, and a link between two vertices can be defined as an edge. Therefore, an undirected graph $\mathbf{G} = (\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{A})$, as shown in Figure 4.3(a), is adopted to represent the graph network of parsing the EEG signal. \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{E} are the sets of vertices and edges, respectively. \mathbf{A} is an adjacency matrix of the graph network \mathbf{G} . $|\mathbf{V}| = N$ represents the number of the vertices in the graph network. The key idea of the adopted STGCN is to consider spatial dependency and temporal dependency at the same

Figure 4.3: (a) A graph structure of partial EEG headset and (b) a graph network in a spatial and temporal space

time. The spatial and temporal dependency of the EEG signals is shown in Figure 4.3(b). The raw EEG signals are defined as $S = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_M) \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times M \times N \times T}$, where W , M , and T denotes the element of a command phrase, the number of samples, and the time-series length of each sample, respectively. Feature matrix of each sample, as the input of the GCN, is defined as $\mathbf{X}_i = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N^i) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F}$, where x_N^i is the defined features of node n at sample i .

Within the STGCN model, a spatial graph convolution is adopted to obtain the spatial features by aggregating information from neighbour nodes, and it is formulated as

$$\mathbf{y} = \sigma(\mathbf{U}g_\theta(\mathbf{L})\mathbf{U}^T\mathbf{x}) \quad (4.8)$$

where Fourier basis $\mathbf{U} = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ decomposes the graph Laplacian as $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$, \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{A} are the degree matrix of the graph and the learned adjacency matrix, respectively. $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{diag}[\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{N-1}] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is the eigenvalue vector of \mathbf{L} . g_θ is a convolution kernel, and \mathbf{x} is the input data. Then, a $K - 1$ order Chebyshev polynomial is used to approximate the graph convolution kernel, and then the spatial information of each node that aggregates 0 to $K - 1$ order neighbours are extracted by applying the Chebyshev graph convolution on the signal [131]. The formula is depicted as follows

$$\mathbf{y} = g_\theta(\mathbf{L}) * \mathcal{G}\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \theta_k T_k(\tilde{\mathbf{L}})\mathbf{x} \quad (4.9)$$

where $*\mathcal{G}$ is graph convolution operation, and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^K$ is the vectors of Chebyshev coefficients. $\tilde{\mathbf{L}} = \frac{2}{\lambda_{max}}\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{I}_N$, where λ_{max} and $\mathbf{I}_N \in [-1, 1]$ are

the maximal eigenvalue of the Laplacian matrix and an identity matrix, respectively. $\mathbf{T}_k(\cdot)$ is the Chebyshev polynomials of K order, where $\mathbf{T}_k(x) = 2x\mathbf{T}_{k-1}(x) - \mathbf{T}_{k-2}(x)$, $\mathbf{T}_1(x) = x$, and $\mathbf{T}_0(x) = 1$. The maximum radius of the convolution from the central nodes is determined by the kernel size of the adopted Chebyshev graph convolution. Therefore, the spatial information of each node that aggregates 0 to $K - 1$ order neighbours is extracted [131].

To extract the temporal information of the EEG signals, a temporal convolution operation within a convolutional neural network layer is performed, and for the input signals, it is formulated as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \text{ReLU}(\Phi * (\text{ReLU}(g_\theta * \mathcal{G}\mathbf{Y}^{l-1}))) \quad (4.10)$$

where Φ and $*$ are the temporal convolution kernel's parameters and operator, respectively.

The variation of the EEG signal in both temporal and spatial spaces may produce the change of the graph structure. A learnable graph structure approach is adopted to dynamically update the adjacency matrix, given by

$$A_{ij} = \exp(\text{ReLU}(w|x_m - x_n|)) / \text{sum}(\exp(\text{ReLU}(w|x_m - x_n|))) \quad (4.11)$$

During this process, certain electrodes may contain valuable information for the feature extraction, compared with other electrodes. To extract key information of such electrodes both in spatial and temporal spaces, a spatial-temporal attention strategy is adopted [132][133]. The spatial attention policy is formulated as follows

$$\mathbf{S}' = \mathbf{U}_s \cdot \sigma(\mathbf{X}^r \mathbf{V}_1 \mathbf{V}_2 \mathbf{V}_3 (\mathbf{X}^r)^T + \mathbf{b}_s) \quad (4.12)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^r = (x_0, \dots, x_{M-1}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M \times C_i}$ is the input of the r -th network layer, $\mathbf{U}_s, \mathbf{b}_s \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\mathbf{V}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^M$, $\mathbf{V}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{C_i \times M}$, and $\mathbf{V}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{C_i}$ are learnable parameters, respectively. σ is the activation function, and \mathbf{S}' is the spatial attention matrix, which is dynamically adjusted by the input of the current layer. The element S'_{ij} in the attention matrix \mathbf{S}' denotes the correlation of nodes i and j , and \mathbf{S}' is normalised by a softmax function.

$$\mathbf{S} = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{S}') \quad (4.13)$$

Then, the temporal attention mechanism is depicted by

$$\mathbf{T}' = \mathbf{O}_t \cdot \sigma(((\mathbf{X}^r)^T \mathbf{P}_1) \mathbf{P}_2 (\mathbf{P}_3 \mathbf{X}^r) + \mathbf{b}_t) \quad (4.14)$$

where $\mathbf{O}_t, \mathbf{b}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, $\mathbf{P}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $\mathbf{P}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{C_i \times N}$, and $\mathbf{P}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{C_i}$ are learnable parameters, respectively. T'_{ij} in \mathbf{T}' denotes correlation strength between nodes i and j . \mathbf{T}' is normalised as \mathbf{T} by a softmax function. Then, the normalised temporal attention matrix \mathbf{T} is defined as the input of the r -th network layer \mathbf{X}^r to get the $\hat{\mathbf{X}}^r = (\hat{\mathbf{X}}_0, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{X}}_{N-1}) = (\mathbf{X}_0, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{N-1})\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times C_i \times M}$ that is used to consider the temporal valuable information.

4.3. FROM BRAINWAVE TO ROBOT CONTROL IN ASSEMBLY

Figure 4.4: Command phrase classification confusion matrix of the proposed STGCN approach for: (a) subjects, (b) predicates, and (c) objects

4.2.2 Experimental results

For training STGCN, an EEG signal dataset composed of 8,584 EEG recordings from healthy subjects is used. 7 time slice EEG signals were used to train the STGCN model with a batch size of 128 and an Adam optimiser with an initial learning rate of 0.01. The training epochs and dropout are 100 and 0.5, respectively. Convolutional filters are appropriated by a 3rd order Chebyshev polynomial, and the graph and standard convolution kernels are 15 and 15, respectively. 10-fold cross-validation is deployed to evaluate the proposed STGCN model. The classification accuracy of the proposed attention-based STGCN method is 87.58%, and the confusion matrices of the classification results for the *subjects*, *predicates*, and *objects* are shown in Figure 4.4(a), (b) and (c), respectively. It can be observed that the classification accuracy of the command words for ‘Robot’ and ‘Human’ are 92.04% and 90.32%, respectively. For the command words of the *Predicates*, the results of classification accuracy for the ‘Place’, ‘Assemble’, and ‘Insert’ are 84.26%, 81.52%, and 85.11%, respectively. For the classification of the component part, the accuracy of the ‘Block’, ‘Cylinder’, and ‘Tube’ is 91.03%, 86.73%, and 89.64%, respectively.

4.3 From brainwave to robot control in assembly

To facilitate robot control and collaborative assembly, this section proposes an AF-based FB network that associates the command phrases with valid robot control commands during assembly and defines assembly planning.

Figure 4.5: Workflow of the ECC for Insert_AF_FB

A set of assembly operations such as insertion, placing, and welding are used to describe an assembly task and each of which is associated with an AF based on assembly logic that defines the assembly sequences of a task. Each AF is handled by an event-driven FB. A detailed introduction of the FB is depicted in Chapter 3. The workflow of the ECC for Insert_AF_FB (an AF-based FB for insertion) is shown in Figure 4.5. The *Insert* event activates the start of the insertion operation after initialisation. With the reference information (*IRef*) and assembly constraints (*ICon*) that includes part information, robot paths for part insertion are generated through executing the *MotionPlanning* state, followed by issuing an *InsertCNF* event for confirmation. During the insertion operation, the orientation and position of the end-effector need to be adjusted to accurately insert the component, and it is facilitated by state switch into the *InsertTarget*. Then, the defined *InsertTargetAlgo* algorithm is executed for insertion operations. Finally, the robot gripper control is performed as the state condition of *WaitforICNF* is satisfied, followed by an *IPartCNF* event output for completion confirmation.

The workflow of the AF-based FB network, as shown in Figure 4.6, starts with the conversion of the EEG signals into command phrases. A SERVER FB serves as a communication channel for listening to the EEG signals from the EEG sensor headset, and a CLIENT FB is adapted to transmit control commands to the robot controllers. All the FBs runs in an IEC 61499 runtime environment (4Diac FORTE). When triggered by an ELEEG event, a command phrase is classified into command words with the *Subjects*, *Predicates*, and *Objects* using a *Classifier* FB, and their values are assigned to the output variables of *VarBot*, *VarAct*, and *VarPart*, respectively. The content of the *Predicates* is associated with the predefined

Figure 4.6: An assembly feature-based function block network for HRC assembly

AF and works as a trigger event to AF-based FBs for assembly operations. Accordingly, the output events of the *Place* and *Insert* activates the AF-based FBs of the *Place_AF_FB* and *Insert_AF_FB*, respectively, in which the assembly reference (*IRef*) and constraint (*ICon*) including part information and constraints serve as the control input of assembly planning and motion planner. The two FBs are responsible for executing placing and insertion operations of the components during assembly, respectively. Finally, robot control commands composed of a set of gripper and motion instructions are sent out for the task execution through the SIFB (CLIENT).

4.4 Experiment

In this section, a set of assembly cases are designed to validate the developed HRC assembly system. Figure 4.7 shows the experimental setup connected with a controller of the industrial robot and an EEG receiver via Ethernet and USB, respectively. The author designed a partial car engine assembly task to demonstrate the performance of the brainwave-driven control approaches in assembly. It involves placing a cylinder head (3.4 kg) onto

Figure 4.7: Experimental setup

an engine block and then accurate insertion of a fuel injector tube (1.8 kg) into the cylinder head’s holes, followed by fastening screws by the human operator.

As shown in Figure 4.8, the assembly process consists of 6 control steps. Step ① starts with a brainwave command ‘*robot place cylinder*’. The SIFB (*SEVER*) transmits the recorded EEG signals to the *Classifier*, and the signals of the command phrases are segmented into command words of the subject, predicate, and object, respectively. The extracted feature matrix of the signals serves as the input to the STGCN model, followed by the output of the classified results. They are context-based command words of ‘*robot*’, ‘*place*’, and ‘*cylinder*’ with the classification accuracy of 84.26%, 81.52%, and 85.11%, as shown in Figure 4.4(b), respectively, and the components of the ‘*Predicates*’ are defined as triggering events to the defined FBs. The values of the *subjects* and *objects* that contain the information of the executor (robot) and part (cylinder) are assigned to *PRobot* and *PPart* variables, respectively. The latter defines the position information of the cylinder and the engine block as well as the grasping position of the cylinder in a robotic coordinate system. The event of the ‘*Place*’ activates the execution of the ‘*Place_AF_FB*’ as shown in Step ②. Within the FB, the gripper and motion control algorithms are executed to generate valid control commands that are executed on the robot controller through the *CLIENT* SIFB. Then, by executing these commands, the robot moves to and grasp the cylinder head with a millimetre tolerance as shown in the inset. Step ③ controls the robot to place the cylinder head on the engine block, and the human operator works with the robot in parallel to adjust the cylinder

Figure 4.8: Assembly sequence and control steps

head and check the quality of the assembly as shown in the inset. Step ④ is to execute the insertion of the tube into the cylinder head's holes, and it is controlled by the brainwave command of '*robot insert tube*'. It is segmented into command words of the '*robot*', '*insert*', and '*tube*', respectively. Triggered by the event of '*Insert*', the '*Insert_AF_FB*' is activated to perform the insertion operation. At the controller level, the generated control commands instruct the robot to move for grasping the tube as shown in the inset. Then, the adjustment of the orientation of the tube for accurate insertion is performed by the robot as shown in Step ⑤. Meanwhile, as shown in the inset, the human operator monitors and checks if the tube is aligned with the holes of the cylinder head. Finally, the human operator screws the components when the robot returns to its initial position in Step ⑥, and the completed assembly of all the components is shown in the inset.

Chapter 5

Sensorless haptic control for HRC assembly

This chapter proposes a novel sensorless haptic approach to manipulate an industrial robot without using any extra sensors and facilitate HRC assembly. This chapter formulates the response to RQ3. The main contributions to this chapter are Papers 1 and 4.

5.1 Industrial robot and collaborative robot

Lightweight collaborative robots are widely used as collaborating partners in assembly lines [3]. Due to built-in sensors, cobots work with incredible precision and are suitable for industries like consumer electronics [7]. In addition, humans can haptically guide the cobots for intuitive and efficient control under the tech-in mode. Cobots are, therefore, adopted to facilitate safe collaboration between humans and robots. However, the low load-bearing capacity of the cobots poses challenges in handling heavy-duty components. For this purpose, industrial robots with high rated payloads are considered a promising solution to meet such needs and are also widely adopted in HRC assembly. However, conventional industrial robots do not have built-in force sensors but are often driven by AC servo systems [9]. Installing haptic devices such as force/torque sensors on such robots is technically challenging and costly [10]. For this purpose, this chapter explores a sensorless haptic approach to HRC assembly that is closely associated with Papers 1 and 4. The performance of the haptic robot control during assembly is heavily affected by the accuracy of the contact force estimation of the robots and force-controlled robot motion.

This chapter starts with an accurate model of the robot dynamics within both sliding and presliding regimes where friction modelling is actively ex-

plored. Then, the external force induced by physical contact with the robot is accurately estimated and then transformed into motion control commands by adopting an adaptive admittance controller. Finally, precise positioning and control of the robots in the collaborative assembly are achieved.

5.2 Contact force estimation

5.2.1 Robot dynamics

The dynamic model of the robot with N DoF is defined as follows

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \boldsymbol{\tau}_f(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) = \boldsymbol{\tau}_m - \boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} \quad (5.1)$$

where $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_m \in \mathbb{R}^N$ are the mass matrix, the centrifugal and Coriolis effects, the gravity, friction and motor torques of the robot joints, respectively. The external torques $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ of the robots related with contact force $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^M$ in Cartesian space are formulated as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} = \mathbf{J}^T(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{F} \quad (5.2)$$

where $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ is the Jacobian matrix.

Firstly, the Stribeck model is adopted to estimate the Stribeck friction in the gross sliding regime, given its capacity on describing many characteristics of friction [86].

$$\mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{F}_c + (\mathbf{F}_s - \mathbf{F}_c)e^{-|\mathbf{v}/\mathbf{v}_s|^\sigma} \text{sign}(\mathbf{v}) + \mathbf{F}_v\mathbf{v} \quad (5.3)$$

where \mathbf{F}_c , \mathbf{F}_s and \mathbf{F}_v are the Coulomb, static and viscous friction, respectively. σ , \mathbf{v}_s and \mathbf{v} are the exponent of the Stribeck nonlinearity, the Stribeck velocity and joint velocity, respectively.

However, the friction at near-zero velocity is important to robot control in the presliding regimes, and it is depicted by a hysteresis relation of the displacement instead of the velocity. The the generalised Maxwell-slip (GMS) model has demonstrated the success of estimating the friction in the presliding regime [88]. The GMS is depicted by a set of parallel \mathbf{N} elasto-slide elements. The hysteresis force \mathbf{F}_i produced by the deflection of the asperity junction between Maxwell-slip elements is depicted as

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if } |z - \varsigma_i| < \frac{W_i}{k_i}, \text{ then } \begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_i = k_i(z - \varsigma_i) \\ \varsigma_i = \text{const} \end{cases} \\ & \text{else } \begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_i = \text{sgn}(z - \varsigma_i)W_i \\ \varsigma_i = z - \text{sgn}(z - \varsigma_i)\frac{W_i}{k_i} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

5.3. ADMITTANCE-BASED COMPLIANT CONTROL

where z , ς_i , k_i and W_i are the common displacement, the position, maximum force, and stiffness of element i , respectively. Therefore, the presliding friction is defined as the sum of the hysteresis force of the N elasto-slide elements and formulated as follows

$$\mathbf{F}_h = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{F}_i \quad (5.5)$$

5.2.2 Prediction of Cartesian contact force

The GMS model describes the friction transition behaviour of the presliding and sliding regimes. To ensure a smooth transition, the threshold velocity is adopted to detect the velocity transition in both the presliding and sliding regimes. With the context, the dynamic model of the robot in both regimes is formulated as

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{F}_h = \tau; |\dot{\mathbf{q}}| < \varepsilon \quad (5.6a)$$

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{F}_f(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) = \tau; |\dot{\mathbf{q}}| \geq \varepsilon \quad (5.6b)$$

where Eqs. 5.6a and 5.6b describe the dynamic models in the presliding and sliding regimes, respectively. Accordingly, the external joint torque is defined as the residual of the measured and estimated joint torques and formulated as

$$\tau_e = \tau_m - \tau_p \quad (5.7)$$

where τ_m and τ_p are the measured feedback joint torque from the robot controller and the predicted joint torques calculated by 5.6a and 5.6b, respectively. Finally, the contact force in Cartesian space is calculated from the external joint torques, given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}} = (\mathbf{J}^T)^\dagger \hat{\tau}_e \quad (5.8)$$

where $\mathbf{J}^{T\dagger} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ is the Moore-Penrose inverse of matrix \mathbf{J}^T , and f is the estimated contact force.

5.3 Admittance-based compliant control

To facilitate robot control and collaborative assembly, admittance control is used to transform the detected contact force into reference displacement and velocity such that humans can control the robot through the applied contact force [95]. The admittance control model is formulated as

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}} = M_p \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + D_p \dot{\mathbf{q}} \quad (5.9)$$

where M_p and D_p are the moments of inertia and the damping, respectively. The admittance model relates the external force to control the robot with translational motion in Cartesian space and rotational operations, respectively. The former is to convert the external force into a displacement and velocity reference (q and \dot{q}), respectively, and the latter is to derive an angular displacement (q) and velocity (\dot{q}), respectively. Therefore, the adaptive haptic robot manipulation is mainly determined by admittance parameters. During collaborative assembly, admittance parameters with low values are adopted to control the robot to quickly approach targets, while fine manipulation with accurate positioning at a low speed is controlled by the admittance parameters with high values. Within the context, adaptive admittance control with online adjustment of the admittance parameters is realised to facilitate efficient robot control based on human preference in assembly, and it is depicted as follows

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{D}_p = D_p + \alpha |\ddot{q}| \text{sign}(\hat{f}) \\ \tilde{M}_p = M_p/D_p(1 - \sigma(1 - e^{\delta(\tilde{D}_p - D_p)}))\tilde{D}_p \end{cases} \quad (5.10)$$

where \tilde{D}_p and \tilde{M}_p are the update of the damping D_p and the inertia M_p , respectively. α and σ are the parameters to tune the damping and the steady state ratio (M_p/D_p), respectively. δ is for the smoothness control associated with the ratio variation.

For the system control at a controller level, the zero-order-hold is used to obtain a discretised desired velocity that is formulated as follows

$$\dot{q}_k = (\hat{f}_k - D_p \dot{q}_{k-1})\Delta t/M_p + \dot{q}_{k-1} \quad (5.11)$$

where \dot{q}_k , \hat{f}_k and Δt are the velocity reference and the torque residual at time t_k , and the discrete-time step, respectively. The formula below depicts the desired position.

$$q_k = (\hat{f}_k - D_p \dot{q}_{k-1})\Delta t^2/2M_p + \dot{q}_{k-1}\Delta t + q_{k-1} \quad (5.12)$$

where q_k is the angular displacement at time t_k .

To convert the contact force into the accurate movement of the robot, the Cartesian components of the contact force are identified to determine the movement direction of the robot, and the Cartesian coordinates of the end-effector ($R^3 \times O(3) = \{x, y, z, \phi, \theta, \psi\}$) are adjusted by the admittance controller. R^3 and $O(3)$ are the position and the Euler angles that specify the end-effector's orientation in Cartesian space, respectively. The state variables describe the Cartesian components of the contact force, and also control the motion of the robot along a reference axis. For the rotational manipulation, Euler angles represent the orientation of the end-effector.

The state variables of $x=1$ and $\phi=1$ control the rotational motion along X-axis. Similarly, the rotations of the end-effector about Y and Z axes can be also determined, respectively. Meanwhile, the first-order derivative of the Euler angle over time determines the angular velocity of the end-effector.

5.4 Experiment

A set of test cases are performed to evaluate the developed HRC assembly system. It starts with parameter identification of the Stribeck model, the GMS model, and the dynamic model of the robot, followed by the test cases of estimating contact force. Then, a case study of a partial car engine assembly is performed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the sensorless haptic control approach.

To eliminate the effect of the centrifugal and Coriolis forces, single joint movement along clockwise and counterclockwise with a constant velocity is performed, in which the joint torque only includes the gravity and friction torques.

$$\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \boldsymbol{\tau}_f(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) = \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (5.13)$$

Then, the joint friction is depicted by

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_f(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) = (\boldsymbol{\tau}^+ - \boldsymbol{\tau}^-)/2 \quad (5.14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}^+$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}^-$ are the joint torques along clockwise and counterclockwise movement of a single joint. \mathbf{q} and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ are the joint position and the constant joint velocity, respectively.

Each robot joint performs the excitation trajectory used for measuring Stribeck friction, and it is the constant velocity-based joint movement with a specific joint angle along with both directions. As shown in Figure 5.1, Joint 3 executes the experimental trajectory at a velocity of 0.314 rad/s. The measured Stribeck friction of Joints 1–6, depicted by blue lines in Figure 5.2, is used for identifying the Stribeck parameters using a sequential quadratic programming method that is a nonlinear solver with super-linear convergence characteristics.

$$\max\left(\sum_1^N (\boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \mathbf{F}_f)^2\right) \leq \epsilon_f \quad (5.15)$$

where ϵ_f is a predefined constant approximation error.

Table 5.1 describes the values of the identified parameters for Joints 1–6 in proper SI units. The predicted friction torque is represented by red lines in Figure 5.2, and the mean square errors (MSEs: N^2m^2) are calculated in Table 5.2. It can be observed that the proposed approach can converge to

Figure 5.1: Excitation signals of Stribeck friction for Joint 3

a small error level. In addition, a relatively big error of Joints 1 and 2 is caused by association with other joints.

Table 5.1: Results of Stribeck parameters for Joints 1 to 6

Joint	F_c	F_s	F_v	v_s	σ
1	15.078	18.834	19.189	0.042	2
2	10.454	13.813	39.466	0.007	2
3	13.157	16.267	12.822	0.024	2
4	5.498	7.998	1.805	0.033	2
5	8.257	12.198	5.842	0.019	2
6	6.073	8.572	3.003	0.020	2

An appropriate selection of the excitation trajectory is critical to the parameter identification of the Maxwell-slip elements. To keep the elements in the presliding regime during the identification, a sine signal with low frequencies and small amplitudes is adopted. The formula of a nonlinear parameter identification problem, as shown in Eq. 5.15, is to obtain the minimal sum of squares of the presliding friction residuals.

The results of parameter identification for Joints 1 to 6 with 5 Maxwell-slip elements are shown in Figure 5.3, where the measured and predicted friction are marked in blue and red lines, respectively. The sampling fre-

Figure 5.2: Results of measured and predicted Stribeck friction for Joints 1 to 6

quency is 83 Hz. For each joint, the reference trajectory, measured friction torque and its variation over the relative displacement are depicted from left to right in Figure 5.3, respectively. In each row, the reference trajectory and the measured friction torque over time, and the measured friction torque over relative displacement are presented from left to right, respectively. The reference trajectory's amplitudes of Joints 1, 2, 3, and 6 are $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ rad, and the those of Joints 4 and 5 are $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ rad, respectively. The friction behaviour obtained by the GMS model for Joints 1 to 6 is described in the third column, and it shows the hysteresis curve with the non-local memory in the presliding regime. The measured joint positions and torques in Figure 5.3 are defined as input of the parameter identification model of the Maxwell-slip elements in Eq. 5.15. Then, the identified parameters of the GMS model with five Maxwell-slip elements in proper SI units are summarised in Table 5.3, and the corresponding MSEs

Table 5.2: MSEs of predicted and measured joint torques for Joints 1 to 6

Joint	1	2	3	4	5	6
MSE	0.9748	1.5469	0.1472	0.0378	0.9829	0.0261

Table 5.3: Results of the GMS parameters for Joints 1 to 6

Para	Joint 1	Joint 2	Joint 3	Joint 4	Joint 5	Joint 6
k_1	87316.6	344458.1	43138.5	13299.9	36590.8	16675.7
W_1	0.803	0.365	4.617	3.435	2.337	2.469
ς_1	$5.52*10^{-5}$	$-2.51*10^{-4}$	$9.74*10^{-5}$	$2.41*10^{-4}$	$-6.64*10^{-4}$	$9.99*10^{-4}$
k_2	87551.7	141051.4	43138.6	13299.3	36590.8	16675.8
W_2	0.800	4.268	4.895	0.195	2.858	1.667
ς_2	$1.36*10^{-4}$	$1.20*10^{-4}$	$-9.91*10^{-4}$	0.001	$-6.92*10^{-5}$	$-1.02*10^{-4}$
k_3	87318.1	308263.7	43138.7	20634.8	36590.7	16675.2
W_3	12.992	7.450	4.916	3.836	1.990	1.617
ς_3	$1.39*10^{-4}$	$-3.45*10^{-4}$	$-9.83*10^{-4}$	$-9.32*10^{-4}$	$9.62*10^{-4}$	$7.33*10^{-4}$
k_4	82181.8	305690.5	43138.2	13299.3	36590.4	16675.9
W_4	3.792	1.136	3.424	0.194	2.692	1.114
ς_4	-0.001	$6.37*10^{-5}$	$6.90*10^{-5}$	0.001	$9.63*10^{-4}$	$-8.11*10^{-5}$
k_5	82183.9	305585.9	43138.4	20635.0	36590.8	16675.8
W_5	0.447	0.594	3.648	0.337	2.321	1.705
ς_5	$-5.12*10^{-4}$	$3.41*10^{-4}$	$6.61*10^{-5}$	$-9.23*10^{-4}$	$-1.45*10^{-4}$	$-9.45*10^{-5}$

are calculated in Table 5.4. The experimental results show that the GMS model performs well on the reduction of the tracking errors.

$$\mathbf{F} = \sum_j^N (\mathbf{F}_h(j) - \hat{\mathbf{F}}_h(j))^2 \quad (5.16)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_h(j)$, N and $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_h(j)$ are the measured presliding friction with the j -th sample, the sample number of experimental data, and the predicted value of the presliding friction with the j -th sample, respectively.

Next, the excitation trajectory of the Finite Fourier series is used to determine the dynamic parameters of the dynamic model of the robot. The formulated dynamic model with known friction is depicted as follows

$$\Phi(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \ddot{\mathbf{q}})\chi + \hat{\tau}_f = \tau + \tau_e \quad (5.17)$$

where Φ , n and m are a $n \times m$ observation matrix, the number of equations and inertial parameters, respectively. $\chi \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the vector of the inertial parameters. $\hat{\tau}_f \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the predicted friction within the presliding and sliding regimes, and a weighted least square method is adopted to identify

Figure 5.3: Results of the GMS model for all the joints

Table 5.4: MSEs of predicted and measured joint torques for Joints 1 to 6

Joint	1	2	3	4	5	6
MSE	0.4979	0.1929	0.1571	0.0559	0.053	0.0235

the parameters. The Finite Fourier series with the minimal objective is depicted as follows

$$\sum_{l=1}^{N_i} \frac{a_l^i}{w_{fl}} \sin(w_{fl}t) - \frac{b_l^i}{w_{fl}} \cos(w_{fl}t) + q_{i,0} \quad (5.18)$$

where a_l^i, b_l^i are the amplitudes. $w_f, N_i, q_{i,0}$ and t indicate the fundamental pulsation and the number of the term of Fourier series, the robot configuration at the start of the original excitation, and the time, respectively. The objective function of minimising the condition number W of Φ is formulated as follows

$$\theta = \underset{t_1}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{t_1}^{t_n} \operatorname{cond}(W) \quad (5.19)$$

where t_n is the data set with n samples.

Here, the five-order Finite Fourier series is adopted as the excitation trajectory to identify the dynamic parameters, followed by a sine trajectory with varying velocities and amplitudes for validating the identified model. To evaluate the effectiveness of the developed approach on the contact force estimation, an appropriate velocity threshold is defined to divide the presliding and sliding regimes, where the value for Joint 3 is 0.0017 rad/s obtained from the trial and error. A low-speed clockwise movement with a small joint angle is firstly performed by Joint 3 such that its presliding friction reaches saturation, which is demonstrated by the maximal deflection of the asperity junctions. Then, a tiny position change on Joint 3 is produced by the trajectory movement of Joint 6, and the produced joint velocity is lower than the defined threshold during this process as shown in Figure 5.4, and this ensures that Joint 3 works in the presliding regime, accompanied with the produced vibration torque on Joint 3. The applied contact force on the robot's end-effector controls Joint 3 to move forward and backward at a velocity slower than the threshold, respectively. The experimental results of the measured and predicted friction, and torque residual of Joint 3 are shown in Figure 5.4(b), (c) and (d), respectively. It can be observed from Figure 5.4(a) that Joint 3 is always in the presliding regime during the whole process, and the maximum deflection of the asperity junctions on the contacting surface of Joint 3 is reached at the initial stage. As shown

Figure 5.4: Torque estimation of Joint 3 in the presliding regime

in Figure 5.4(d), the torque residual shows that the contact force is applied and detected on the robot at about 17 s and 24 s, as indicated by Areas A and B, respectively. The black dash-dot lines mark the threshold of the detectable external force with 2 Nm. Given the elements of the unmodelled parameters and backlash, the performance of the developed approach on the external force detection is well demonstrated.

Finally, a case study of a partial engine assembly is deployed to validate the developed sensorless haptic control approach. The experimental setup is connected with a KUKA robot (KR 6 R700 Sixx) with a KR C4 controller that equips KUKA System Software 8.3 [134], as shown in Figure 5.5. The joint position and torque of an axis can be obtained by accessing the system variable `AXIS_ACT_MEAS` and `TORQUE_AXIS_ACT`, respectively. The communication frequency is 83 Hz on average, and given the human hand movement frequency of 5–10 Hz, a filter with a cut-off frequency of 5 Hz is defined. `JOpenShowVar` [135], as the middleware between the KUKA

Figure 5.5: Experimental setup

Robot Language and the user programme through TCP/IP, is adopted to collect the feedback data of robot joint positions and torques and send control commands to the controller. The experimental results of the contact force estimation along the Z axis, position and speed reference values are depicted in Figure 5.6. The detection of the contact force starts at $t=0$ when the weight is added to the robot's end-effector. Then, the contact force produced by the weights is decreased as they are removed at T_1, T_2, and T_3, respectively, which are depicted by green dashed lines, and the position and speed reference accordingly show the corresponding variation. It can be observed that the threshold of the contact force estimation is 3.5 N since the position and speed of the robot in Cartesian space do not change at this time slice as shown in Area A. The detectable minimum contact force can be affected by the parameter uncertainty of the dynamic model, the noise of feedback signals from the robot controller, and the unmodelled elements of the robot dynamics.

The assembly task involves inserting a fuel injection tube (1.8 kg) into four holes of a cylinder head of a car engine, led by a human operator. The assembly process includes 10 control steps as shown in Figure 5.7. The initial configuration of the robot $\{q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5, q_6\} = \{0^\circ, -90^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 37^\circ\}$

Figure 5.6: Results of position, velocity, and contact force in Cartesian space

is shown in Step ❶. Step ❷ controls the robot gripper to approach the fuel injection tube, which is implemented by applying the force onto the robot's end-effector. In Steps ❸ and ❹, the human operator applies the force on the far-end of Joint 3 from the bottom and then top, respectively. During this process, the friction direction of Joint 3 is changed twice, from positive Z-axis to negative Z-axis and then positive Z-axis again, and this is defined as 'open/close' control command of the robot gripper. The orientation of the end-effector is adjusted to well align the grippers with the tube with a tolerance of less than 2 mm, which is facilitated by the rotational admittance control in Step ❺. Step ❻ is to execute the 'close' of the robot gripper by using the applied force. Step ❼ controls the robot to quickly approach the assembly target before an accurate positioning at a low speed. A fine manipulation in Step ❽ is performed to control the tube's orientation and position for accurate insertion, followed by the final insertion of the tube into the holes. Finally, the operator applies the force on the robot to open the gripper. The performance and effectiveness of the sensorless haptic approach to HRC assembly are well demonstrated in its adaptability and flexibility. To demonstrate the experimental results during assembly, the results of Joint 3 in terms of motion parameters, admittance parameters,

Figure 5.7: Sensorless haptic control to HRC assembly

and torque signals are shown in Figure 5.8, where the initial values of D_p and M_p are $50 \text{ Nm} \cdot \text{s/rad}$ and 20 kg/m^2 , respectively. Figure 5.8(a), (b) and (c) shows the joint angle, velocity, and acceleration of Joint 3, respectively. Accordingly, the measured joint torque, the predicted torque, and torque residual are shown in Figure 5.8(e), (f) and (g), respectively. Admittance parameters of the inertial and damping are depicted in Figure 5.8(d) and (h), respectively. It can be observed that the applied force on the robot produces a clear variation of the motion parameters. Meanwhile, the admittance parameters of the inertial and damping vary accordingly with the change of the torque residual. The experimental results of Figure 5.8 in the blue area demonstrate that the starting motion of Joint 3 shows a rapid acceleration stage with a high velocity, and the damping accordingly changes. The area between the green dashed lines indicates the fitting operation of the tube into the gripper through adjusting the orientation of the end-effector.

Figure 5.8: Results of sensorless haptic HRC assembly for partial car engine components

Chapter 6

Leveraging multimodal data in robot control for HRC assembly

The main contributions to this chapter are Papers 2 and 5. This chapter presents a novel multimodal robot control approach to HRC assembly leveraging multimodal data and event-driven FBs. It starts with the system design of multimodal HRC and then provides an FB-based multimodal interface design for data fusion and algorithm invocation and execution. Leveraging the deep learning algorithms developed in previous chapters, the multimodal data are classified and transformed into valid robot control commands for collaborative assembly. Finally, an engine-assembly case study is used to validate the effectiveness of the developed system for HRC assembly.

Applications of using multimodal data to support HRC assembly have been actively explored [5][48]. Despite the use of multimodal data in HRC, complex assembly facilitated by the use of multimodal control becomes less practical and flexible. This is because the current approach uses a step-by-step control execution mode that lowers the efficiency of the collaborative assembly [76]. A huge amount of commands are needed to finish a complex or complicated assembly task because each of the assembly operations (features) that determines an assembly task can be completed by a set of human-dictated commands [13]. This motivates the efficient use of the multimodal commands in HRC assembly, and also leveraging multimodal commands for adaptive robot control in HRC assembly remains a challenge. The HRC scenarios can be defined as single, multiple, and team settings. The current study of HRC is mainly focused on the collaboration of one human and one robot in the context of manufacturing and assembly [3]. However, the collaboration between robot teams and one human operator in assembly is not fully considered and explored [27], and the human operator working with a robot team is common for enhanced efficiency in today's

factory. The difference of the collaborative settings can be reflected in robot workspace and control, human-robot interface design, collaborative modes, and dynamic assembly planning. Within the context, the issue of the incompatibility of the robot interfaces poses a challenge on the human-robot interface design and the data fusion of the human commands [97]. To enhance the efficiency of the HRC assembly, humans working in parallel with a robot or robot team is worth consideration, and this empowers the collaborative modes of ‘robots-assisting-humans’ and ‘humans-assisting-robots’ primitives [35]. The former case treats robots as collaborative partners to help humans perform the tasks that exceed human ability, and in the latter case, human operators use competence not only to give assistance to robots such as delivering easy and light tasks but also use human intelligence to train robots on what to do and explain how to do [19]. When robots work with human operators in close proximity, safe and accurate motion control and manipulation of the robots turn out to be a difficulty because the adaptive adjustment of the motion parameters during assembly cannot be executed for compliant control to changes in the HRC environment [5][76].

This also poses challenges to command conversion from multimodal data to valid robot control commands, in which a function used for associating multimodal data to robot motion control is necessary. Within the context of multimodal control, human commands (voice, gesture, haptics, brainwave, etc.) collected from a multi-sensor perception system are defined as trigger signals to robot control in assembly. However, multimodal data-driven robot control is challenged by the following factors: 1) accurate command classification approaches; 2) robust multimodal command fusion under simultaneous inputs; 3) precise trigger of control modalities.

For this purpose, this chapter presents a novel approach to adaptive robot control in collaborative assembly using multimodal commands. Diverse communication channels between robots and human operators are deployed to collect multimodal human instructions. A programming-free multimodal interface driven by FBs is developed for command fusion, classification, and identification, and the identified commands are defined as inputs to the algorithms of assembly planning. Finally, a multimodal robot control approach is developed for the transformation from the multimodal commands to robot control and assembly execution.

6.1 System design & multimodal interaction

This section presents a system design of multimodal HRC in assembly as shown in Figure 6.1. It includes three modules for effective and efficient HRC assembly. Module ❶ starts with the deployment of a multi-sensor perception system for the collection of the human commands, and data processing algo-

6.1. SYSTEM DESIGN & MULTIMODAL INTERACTION

Figure 6.1: System design of multimodal robot control in assembly

gorithms are executed for command identification and classification. Module ② receives multimodal signals using an FB-based multimodal interface and subsequently performs data fusion as well as command identification and translation that is facilitated by the developed deep learning-based classification systems, and then an FB network with algorithms in ECCs is developed to generate commands of robot control and assembly, which are sent to a module ③ via a robot interface, followed by execution of adaptive robot control and collaborative assembly.

The multi-sensor system in Module ① consists of a sensor headset, a microphone device, robot controllers and a Leap-Motion sensor. They are for collecting EEG signals, voice instructions, feedback data of joint angles and torque, and gesture commands. These signals are transmitted for command fusion and classification through a multimodal interface. After data fusion, the deep learning-based command classification system is for high-accuracy command classification, and the identified commands work as triggering events to the execution of the FB. Within the FB network, the FBs used for command conversion are executed to translate the multimodal commands into robot control commands, and subsequently, a multimodal

control approach embedded in the FBs is performed for fine manipulation of the robot and controlling the predefined modalities. Finally, the results of the valid robot control commands are executed on the robot controller to complete the collaborative assembly tasks. Therefore, multimodal robot control during assembly can be achieved by the use of the FBs with control algorithms together with high-level commands triggering the running of the algorithms for assembly planning and control.

Figure 6.2: Multimodal robot control in assembly

6.2 Multimodal human-robot collaboration in assembly

This section starts with multimodal command collection and fusion, and control modalities for HRC assembly. To facilitate multimodal HRC in assembly, a multimodal robot control approach for HRC assembly is developed leveraging multimodal command fusion driven by FBs, as shown in Figure 6.2. Within the context of HRC, multimodal human commands can be used as a triggering mechanism to an FB network for collaborative assembly and robot control, and four control modalities between one human operator and a robot team are designed for efficient HRC assembly, and they are sensorless haptic, voice and gesture-based, and brainwave-driven control modalities, respectively.

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Figure 6.3: Structure and ECC unit of the Sig.Proc.FB

The developed approach allows human operators to use diverse commands to control robots during collaborative assembly. According to the discussions in previous chapters, the definition and functionalities of voice-and-gesture-based robot control, sensorless haptic control, and brainwave-driven robot control during assembly are represented in Chapters 3, 4 and 5, respectively. For the multimodal commands, precise identification of the types of instructions is critical to accurately trigger the related control modalities. For this purpose, a BFB (*Sig.Proc.FB*) is developed for multimodal command processing and type classification, which is crucial for the correct invocation of FBs and free switch of control modalities, and its structure and ECC are shown in Figure 6.3. The data inputs of *IS.INFO* and *IN.FOR* receive the command information and formats when triggered by the input events. The workflow starts with the status of *START* and then switches into *STATE* which is composed of *INI*, *RUN* and *UPDATE*. Each state controls the execution of the related algorithms, and finally the state changes to *START* again after outputting the event and data. The identified types of commands are generated as the output of the *IS.TYPE*.

To facilitate HRC assembly, an FB network is designed where multimodal commands serve as triggering events to data fusion of the human commands, adaptive robot control, and execution of collaborative assembly, as shown in Figure 6.4. The FB network consists of a set of FBs used for communication, command classification, robot control, and assembly planning. It consists of *SERVER.SIFB*, *CLIENT.SIFB*, *Haptics.FB*, *Gesture.FB*, *EEG.FB*, and *Voice.FB*. The workflow of the FB network starts with communication between multi-sensors and the *SIFBs* that build a link of communication and device access in-between. The *Server.SIFB* receives and collects the multimodal data using a TCP/IP (client/server) communication protocol, and it runs in 4Diac FORTE which is an IEC 61499 runtime environment compiled with C++ implementation. The interface of the *SERVER.SIFB* is depicted in Figure 6.5. The data inputs of *Force*, *EEG*, *Voice*, and *Gesture* receive the feedback data of force/torque, brain-

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Figure 6.4: A function block network for multimodal robot control in assembly

waves, voice and hand gesture signals, respectively. It is facilitated by the live monitoring function of the 4Diac allows event and data inputs/outputs to be listened to online as the FBs run.

Each multimodal command is collected through the data inputs of the SIFB, and the CLIENT_SIFB sends the control and assembly commands to robot controllers for robot control and HRC assembly. Voice_FB is for the conversion of the voice commands into valid robot motion commands in Cartesian space; Gesture_FB is to use hand gestures for robot gripper control, especially in robotic assembly; and EEG_FB provides multimodal support for robot control, as an alternative to auditory and gesture instructions, and it uses brainwaves to directly control the robot in assembly when human hands are occupied not to pose a gesture or unreliable voice recognition within a noisy environment. The three control modalities form a contactless control approach for robot control and collaborative assembly. In addition, Haptics_FB is to allow human operators to directly use their hands for fine manipulation of the robot, and it offers a contact-based control approach. Therefore, the contactless and contact-based approaches provide more flexibility and adaptability for HRC assembly.

To demonstrate the working principle of the SEVER_FB, the workflow

Figure 6.5: Interface of Server_SIFB

Figure 6.6: ECC of Server_SIFB

of its ECC is depicted, which controls the state transition, algorithm execution and control output. When triggered by the input event of *INIT*, the *Server_SIFB* is initialised by executing the initialisation algorithm, and then confirms the complete initialisation by the output event of *INITO*. Followed by the arrival of the input event *RSP*, the state of the *Server_SIFB* is switched into an execution state, and the data streaming of the multimodal commands is online listened to as the condition flag is *TRUE*. The embedded algorithms composed of *EEGAlgo*, *VoiceAlgo*, *ForceAlgo*, and *GestureAlgo* are executed to classify the types of the commands as the output of the signals, followed by execution confirmation through the output event of *CNF*.

6.3 From multimodal data to robot control in HRC assembly

This section presents command translation from multimodal commands to valid robot control commands used for adaptive robot control and collab-

Figure 6.7: Multimodal robot control

orative assembly. A brief introduction of the conversion workflow for four types of control modalities is presented in Figure 6.7(a), (b), (c) and (d), respectively.

Six types of the voice commands that are ‘Forward’, ‘Backward’, ‘Left’, ‘Right’, ‘Up’, and ‘down’ are used to control the robot motion in Cartesian space. As Shown in Figure 6.7(a), ‘Forward’, ‘Left’, and ‘Up’ are used to control the motion along ‘X+’, ‘Y+’, and ‘Z+’, respectively. A relative-translational motion with adaptive motion parameters is performed where an embedded human-machine interface is developed for adjustment of the parameters. Figure 6.7(b) shows the gripper control scheme driven by hand gestures. Two types of hand gestures that are named ‘Gesture 1’ and ‘Gesture 2’ are used to control the close and open of the robot grippers. For the haptic control as shown in Figure 6.7(c), the detected contact force is defined as the input to the admittance controller with adaptive parameters, and the reference position and velocity are generated to control the robot movement. Figure 6.7(d) shows the scheme of brainwave-driven robot control in assembly. The ‘Subjects’, ‘Predicates’, and ‘Objects’ of the brainwave signal are translated to represent the executor, action, and parts

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Figure 6.8: Experimental setup

to be acted on, respectively. The ‘Subjects’ consists of the part information in assembly reference, which is defined as the input to the algorithms of motion planning and gripper control, as shown in ‘*Algo1*’ and ‘*Algo2*’, respectively. Finally, the control commands generated by the four control modalities are executed by the robot controller for adaptive robot control and assembly execution.

To demonstrate the developed system for HRC assembly, a case study of a partial car engine assembly is performed. Figure 6.8 shows the experimental setup connected with the robot controller and multi-sensor devices. The latter consist of a microphone sensor, a Leap Motion sensor, and an EEG sensor headset that are deployed to an external computer. The assembly tasks involve placing a cylinder head (3.4 kg) onto the engine block, followed by a valve cover placed on it, and accurate insertion of an injector fuel tube (1.8 kg) into the cylinder head’s holes. Finally, the human operator inserts four ignition coils into the holes of the cylinder head and then fasten screws.

The HRC assembly process shown in Figure 6.9 includes 12 control steps driven by the multimodal commands and FBs. The assembly starts with Step ① where a brainwave command of ‘*robot place cylinder*’ as a form of the EEG signal is transmitted for command segment through an SIFB. Then, the ‘Subject’, ‘Predicate’, and ‘Object’ of the command phrase are segmented and processed as a feature matrix that is defined as the input to the developed STGCN algorithm. After classifying the commands, each

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Figure 6.9: Assembly sequence and control steps

command word of ‘robot’, ‘place’, and ‘cylinder’ is identified and defined as triggering events to the FB network, and the ‘Predicates’ of the command phrase is associated with the assembly feature-based FB. The time of the signal transmission from the EEG sensor headset to the FB runtime environment (4Diac) takes up to 21 milliseconds on average. Then, triggered by the ‘Place’ event, the information of the part and the executor that is represented by the *subjects* and *objects* respectively is loaded as the input to the *Place_FB* that embeds the algorithms of the assembly planning and gripper control. The generated gripper control commands and motion paths are sent out as the output of the ‘*APath*’ and ‘*ASGrip*’, respectively, through the *SERVER_SIFB*. Then, the cylinder head is controlled to move to the engine block as shown in the inset of Step ①. Adaptive adjustment of the motion parameters enables fine manipulation of the robot and accurate assembly operations at a low speed such as grasping the component. Step

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② shows that the robot is controlled to well fit the gripper's fingers within the holes of the cylinder head. To enhance the efficiency of the collaborative assembly, the human operator works in parallel to check if the gripper is well fitted with the cylinder head. The status of the robot gripper is shown in the inset of Step ②. Then, the hand gesture-based control approach is adopted to control the gripper. As shown in Step ③, the state of the robot gripper is converted into 'close' by using 'Gesture 1' shown in the inset, and this is controlled by the *Gesture_FB* where the gripper control algorithm is triggered to generate the close command. After grasping the cylinder head, it is controlled to be placed onto the engine block in Step ④, and the human operator checks the quality of aligning the cylinder head with the engine block (as shown in the inset). During this process, the robot is controlled to quickly approach the assembly target with a high speed of 100 mm/s and for accurate assembly operations at a low speed of 10 mm/s. To release the gripper, Step ⑤ is to use 'Gesture 2' (as shown in the inset) to open the robot gripper. During this process, the gesture is finally converted into a DO signal that is executed for the gripper control at the controller level.

Next, the human operator uses voice commands to perform the assembly of the valve cover. This is facilitated by a function of the voice commands into the motion plan as shown in Figure 6.7(a). This process starts with issuing the voice commands that are defined as the input to the classification algorithm, and the identified commands serve as the triggering events to the *Voice_FB* that executes the translation from voice commands to valid robot control commands. The generated commands composed of a relative replacement and a velocity are used to control the robot motion. Here, three voice commands are used to control the robot to pick up the valve cover from the engine block in Step ⑥, and they are 'Up', 'Left', and 'Down', respectively. The 'Left' commands generate the relative displacements of 693.39 millimetres with a velocity of 100 mm/s. When the robot gripper is controlled to grasp the valve cover, a hand gesture with 'Gesture 1' is used to close the robot gripper. After that, Step ⑦ controls the robot to place the valve cover onto the cylinder head using the voice command, and the hand gesture as shown in the inset is posed to control the opening of the gripper. The complete assembly of the valve cover is shown in the inset.

Then, the sensorless haptic control approach is used to accurately insert the fuel injector tube into the cylinder head's holes. The workflow starts with building a valid connection with the KUKA robot controller (KRC4) facilitated by a communication switch developed, followed by the data collection. During the sensorless haptic control, the minimal contact force that can be detected is 2 Nm, and the detected contact force is defined as the input to the adaptive admittance controller that generates the reference po-

Figure 6.10: Experimental results of the sensorless haptic control in assembly: (a) angle of Joints 1–3, (b) angle of Joints 4–6, (c) external torques of Joints 1–3, and (d) external torques of Joints 4–6

sition and velocity. In Step ⑧, the human operator applies the force on the end-effector of the robot that is located at the original position, and the robot is forced to move smoothly to the fuel injector tube. During this process, the adaptive parameters with low values are adopted for high-speed movement as shown in the inset, and fine manipulation of the robot is performed for accurate control operations by using high-value admittance parameters. Step ⑨ controls the robot to perform the appropriate fit of the gripper into the fuel injector tube, and this process demonstrates the performance of the admittance controller on accurate motion control. As shown in the inset, the hand gesture is used to close the gripper. In Step ⑩, the robot is controlled to move the fuel injector tube to the engine

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block and align it with the hole of the cylinder head, and one haptic control operation during this process is shown in the inset. Accurate insertion of the fuel injector tube into the holes is executed in Step ⑪, and adaptive adjustment of the orientation and position of the end-effector is deployed in this control step, followed by the open of the robot gripper as shown in the inset. Finally, the operator executes accurate insertion of the ignition coils and then fastens screws to secure the components in Step ⑫, and the inset shows the final assembly result of a partial car engine.

From Step ⑧ to Step ⑪, the developed haptic control approach allows the human operator to haptically control the robot for collaborative assembly, and Figure 6.10(a) and (b) shows the angle of Joints 1–3 and 4–6, respectively. Figure 6.10(c) and (d) shows the joint torque of Joints 1–3 and 4–6, respectively. As shown in Figure 6.10(a), Areas A and C indicate the operations of the gripper control by hand gestures, and Areas D and F of Figure 6.10(c) demonstrate no contact force applied on the robot accordingly. Area B represents the process of securing the components, and no contact force is detected in the corresponding Area E of Figure 6.10(c).

Chapter 7

Discussion and future work

This chapter discusses and answers the research questions proposed in Chapter 1 using the results of the appended papers, followed by highlighting future research directions.

7.1 Responses to research questions

The four research questions presented in this thesis find answers below.

7.1.1 Responses to RQ1

How to leverage verbal and nonverbal commands (voice and gestures) for intuitive robot control during collaborative assembly, specifically for robot motion and gripper control?

This research question is about voice and gesture-based HRC in assembly. It has been jointly answered by Papers 2 and 5. Paper 2 presents the methods of signal collection of the voice and hand gestures, feature extraction that serves as the input to the deep learning algorithms used for command identification and classification. Here, deep CNN and LSTM are adopted to train and identify the voice and hand gesture commands, respectively, and the identified verbal and non-verbal commands are translated into valid robot control commands. Specifically, the voice commands are used to control the robot motion in Cartesian space, and hand gestures are adopted to control the robot grippers. Paper 2 demonstrates voice-and-hand gesture-based control approaches by an experiment of a partial car engine assembly. Also, Paper 5 uses the developed approaches in the HRC assembly of a partial car engine.

CHAPTER 7. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

In HRC assembly, the robot control approaches based on rigid programmes used today can no longer support efficient HRC. This is because the effort on the conventional robot programming in a dynamic yet constrained environment of HRC is large, and changes in the environment of HRC assembly may trigger the reprogramming and re-planning of assembly tasks. With such context, programming an industrial robot envisioned for future factory's shopfloors would be no longer just about coding instructions using a low-level programming language. As the technology behind robotics continues to evolve, varying approaches to facilitating robot programming and simplifying the control for end-users have been reported in [3][44][48]. Some of the commonly used approaches are summarised as 1) the teach-in method of robot programming, 2) play-back programming, 3) lead-through programming, 4) programming by demonstration. However, these methods can no longer satisfy the needs of HRC during assembly because of the limitations of these methods such as the poor transferability to robot systems in a large shared workspace and the difficult deployment of the heavy-duty industrial robots.

The advancement of sensor technologies motivates the wide application of multi-sensors in the HRC assembly, and multimodal intuitive programming offers an opportunity for robot programming without specialised expert knowledge. Multimodality means the use of diverse communication channels between operators and robots. This thesis uses voice instructions to facilitate intuitive robot control and efficient HRC. However, the robot cannot directly understand and know how to execute these commands. For this purpose, the voice instructions are trained and classified by using the deep CNN model, and then the identified instructions are translated into valid robot control commands, which is facilitated by an event-driven FB network with smart algorithms.

In addition, HRC assembly, especially in an automotive field, often needs the operations of grasping the components, which mainly involves the gripper control. Within the context of a robotic assembly, the conventional method of robot manipulation relies on pre-programming codes. However, the change in the HRC environment such as position and environmental variations may trigger a lot of repetitive tasks of the robot programming. To align with intuitive robot control and also address such a challenge, hand gestures are adopted to control the close and open of the robot gripper. Similar to using voice for robot control, accurate translation of the hand gestures into gripper control commands is critical to reliable robot control. The collected hand gestures from the Leap Motion sensor are processed and saved as a feature vector with three elements that are defined as the input to the LSTM model. Then, the identified hand gestures are converted into a digital signal using a formulated transmission function. At the controller,

7.1. RESPONSES TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

the DO channel is created to receive the value of the digital signal. Two types of hand gestures are finally selected to control the open and close of the robot gripper.

The developed voice-and hand gesture-driven control approaches to HRC assembly can facilitate the flexibility and efficiency of assembly operations and free human operators from tedious conventional robot programming. The former contributes to flexible motion control of the robot in Cartesian space with fewer efforts and the latter eases the work of frequent gripper control during the robotic assembly.

7.1.2 Responses to RQ2

How to use brainwave signals to directly control robots in the collaborative assembly in a constraint yet dynamic environment?

Papers 3 and 5 answer the research questions from the motivation of using brain robotics, brainwave signal collection and processing, feature extraction, deep learning algorithms for signal classification and generation of valid robot control commands for adaptive robot control and collaborative assembly. An experiment of a partial car engine assembly is conducted to validate the developed system.

The production and manufacturing sections are mainly in place at the factory shopfloors. The background noise often poses a typical challenge to reliable recognition of the voice instructions. In the context of HRC, human operators may handle other tasks by hand and are unable to make gestures. The voice and hand gestures are originally issued and controlled by human brains, and the question is why not use brainwaves to directly control the robot during assembly. Brainwaves work as a new emerging communication modality and can be used for robot control for seamless HRC assembly. For this purpose, the author decides the use of the brainwaves for intuitive robot control and collaborative assembly. The brain's nervous system is complicated, and a grey structure that is composed of nerve cells is the main part of the cerebral cortex. The limited knowledge of neuroscience poses challenges to the understanding and parsing of brainwave signals. A brainwave command can be issued in the forms of (silent) language, memory and/or vision when using different parts of the brain, and this makes it difficult for brainwave signal processing. Determined by how the brain is used, the patterns behind the brainwaves could be quite different even for the same command. Motivated by the advancement of BCIs, many sensor headsets used for collecting the brainwaves have been developed, and the commonly used approach for signal collection is assisted by the use of external stimuli such as visual aids. However, it is impractical and not suitable

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for HRC assembly in the shopfloors of today's factories. To address this challenge, the author proposes a stimulus-free method for the collection of the brainwave command phrase, and a novel approach to parse the brainwave commands from a semantic perspective is developed. Compared with stimulus-based brainwave signals, stimulus-free brainwave signals may have weaker patterns. To extract the patterns behind the signals, a customised rule is designed to instruct the human operators to issue a command, which is presented in Paper 3.

As can be seen from the thesis, brainwave signal processing with high accuracy is critical to robust robot control and reliable HRC assembly, and the selection of the appropriate method is vital for this purpose. The study on feature extraction of the EEG signals is often categorised in a time domain, a frequency domain, and a time-frequency domain. Raw or pre-processed time-domain EEG signals and frequency transform of the raw EEG signals are used to generate time-domain and frequency-domain features, respectively, while the time-frequency feature includes both time and frequency information. The author uses wavelet transform to convert the time-domain EEG signals into time-frequency information that is defined as the input to the deep learning-based command classification system. Within the context, the selection of the base wavelets and the use of the deep learning algorithm is important to maximise the information extraction and classification accuracy of brainwave commands. A comprehensive study on the base wavelets in terms of the energy-to-Shannon entropy ratio is performed, and finally, the 'Morlet' base wavelet is selected because of its maximal mean value of the energy-to-Shannon entropy ratio. In parallel, the studies on EEG signal classification show that CNNs and RNNs have good performances on the EEG classification, in which the grid data such as feature matrices are defined as the input, but without consideration of the spatial connection among the channels. Given the non-Euclidean data structure of the EEG signals, an undirected graph network is adopted to represent the EEG signals, and this is determined by the substantial fact that sensor channels are considered as the vertices and the links between vertices are treated as the edges.

The success of the STGCN in revealing the spatial and temporal dependency makes it efficient to capture the spatial-temporal information of the EEG signals at the same time. The author develops a novel STGCN model to train and identify each command word of the brainwave command phrases, and the detailed introduction of the model is presented in Paper 5. The classification results demonstrate the performances of the STGCN model in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency. After signal classification, an FB network is developed to apply the brainwaves for intuitive robot control and efficient collaborative assembly. Within the FB network,

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the ‘Predicates’ of the brainwave commands serve as the triggering event to the execution of the assembly feature (AF)-based FBs that are for assembly planning and adaptive robot control. The brainwaves commands are then translated into the valid control commands that are used for adaptive robot control and execution of assembly tasks. Finally, the developed system driven by brainwaves and FBs is validated by a case study of car component assembly.

7.1.3 Responses to RQ3

How to develop a sensorless haptic approach for adaptive industrial robot control and efficient HRC assembly without using any external sensors?

The detailed answers to this research question can be mainly found in Paper 1, and partial work of Paper 4 answers the question of the sensorless contact force estimation. The sensorless haptic control approach for HRC assembly is facilitated by the accurate contact force estimation enabled by the robot dynamic model in presliding and sliding regimes and adaptive admittance control for reference movement translation, followed by the control steps of the assembly operations.

The sensorless haptic control offers contact-based support to multimodal HRC in assembly, as an alternative to contactless approaches such as voice, hand gesture, and brainwave-driven control methods. It allows human operators to use their hands to haptically control the robots without the assistance of any external sensors. However, as can be observed from this thesis, no systematic solution and methodology are available yet. Collaborative robots that are designed for safe operations (Universal Robots) can be haptically manipulated by human operators. However, heavy-duty industrial robots are widely deployed in the manufacturing and production shopfloors, such as automotive assembly lines, due to the large payload and workspace. The commonly used solutions to haptic control of industrial robots are facilitated by extra hardware/assistive systems such as force sensors. This turns out to be a bottleneck on the wide applications in HRC assembly because of costly sensors and technical challenges. The author is motivated to explore a sensorless control approach. This approach starts with accurate contact force estimation. The author explores the precise robot dynamic model in the presliding and sliding regimes. Meanwhile, friction in the mechanical system is critical to the control performance. This thesis also considers the accurate friction model of the presliding and sliding regimes. The Stribeck model is used to capture the friction in the sliding regimes and the GMS model is adopted to build the presliding friction, given its success on the estimation of the friction behaviour in the presliding regime. Finally, the

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contact force with the minimal threshold value of 3.5 N in Cartesian space can be detected, and the minimal detectable joint torque in the joint space can be up to 1.5 Nm.

Next, the key question is how to achieve force-controlled robotic manipulation in assembly. Specifically, the solutions to translate the detected contact force into robot motion control during assembly need to be developed. For this purpose, a comprehensive study of the compliant control is performed, and the results show that impedance and admittance control strategies are often adopted for compliant control. The admittance control is to convert the contact force into reference positions and velocities for motion control. However, both fine manipulation of the robot for accurate control operations in close proximity and high-speed robot motion for efficient assembly operations are necessary for HRC assembly. Adaptive admittance control during assembly turns out to be a challenge for wide acceptance of HRC. To facilitate reliable compliant control, the author develops an adaptive admittance controller with online adjustment of admittance parameters. Through adjustment of the admittance parameters, a fine movement with large values of these parameters is performed for accurate positioning, and those of lower values are selected to generate a robot movement with a high velocity. In addition, it is of paramount importance to ease the haptic robot control for human operators. This is determined by the efficient identification of Cartesian components of the applied contact force, which decides the direction of the robot motion. The admittance controller is adopted to adjust the Cartesian coordinate of the end-effector of the robot, and it is depicted by a set of state variables. The Cartesian components of the contact force are used to perform a translational movement along a reference axis. The rotational movement about a coordinate axis is determined by Euler angles, and the angular velocity is calculated by the first-order derivative of the Euler angle. Finally, the developed haptic control system in HRC assembly is evaluated and validated by an assembly experiment of the car engine parts. The experimental results show that the estimation quality of the contact force can reach up to high accuracy, in which very small magnitudes of external torques and force can achieve robust compliance control. Meanwhile, the haptic control scheme allows the human operator to achieve flexible and fine manipulation of the robot in a natural and easy way during collaborative assembly.

7.1.4 Responses to RQ4

How to develop a multimodal control approach to facilitate reliable collaborative assembly and adaptive robot control, within the context of the collaboration between a human operator and a robot team?

7.1. RESPONSES TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research question is about the multimodal HRC in assembly and it questions the use of multimodal commands composed of voice, gesture, sensorless haptics and brainwaves for efficient HRC assembly. This research question finds the answers in Paper 5. Meanwhile, Papers 1 and 4 offer the answer to contact force estimation and the sensorless haptic control strategy, Paper 2 provides the approaches to process, classify, and identify the voice and hand gestures, and translate them into valid robot control commands, and also the answers to apply brainwaves to intuitively controlling the robots and assisting collaborative assembly can be found in Paper 3.

The multimodality indicates the use of the diverse communication channels between robots and humans for intuitive interaction. For this purpose, a multi-sensor perception system is necessary to be deployed in the HRC environment, and it is composed of an EEG sensor headset, a microphone sensor, a Leap Motion sensor, and connected robot controllers. Each sensor is supported by the developed programs for signal collection. Then, the multimodal signals pose a big challenge on the data fusion as their structures and formats are different. The first step of the data fusion is to identify the types of these commands and associate them with different control modalities. Meanwhile, the multimodal interface design is critical to fusion, invocation, and execution of the diverse commands. For this purpose, the author explores the use of an FB network in the interface design, given the success of FBs on event-and-algorithm-driven robot control. Within the FB network, algorithms used for command classification, robot control and collaborative assembly are developed and executed through an event-driven triggering mechanism, and four types of the CFBs are defined and associated with four types of control commands. They are for sensorless haptic, voice, gesture, and brainwave-driven robot control. Each CFB is composed of a set of basic FBs where these high-level multimodal commands serve as the triggering events to the execution of the embedded algorithms.

Next, command classification with high accuracy determines the precise execution of the robot control and assembly operations. Targeting this question, the author presents a deep learning-driven command classification system for low-latency and high-accuracy robot control, and the well-trained classification models are embedded in the FB network. The detailed deep learning algorithms have been presented in Papers 2, 3 and 5, respectively, and the sensorless control scheme composed of contact force estimation and motion control is presented in Papers 1 and 4. In addition, the robot controller cannot directly understand these multimodal human commands that need to be translated into valid robot control commands. This involves assembly planning and adaptive robot control during HRC assembly. However, complex or complicated assembly tasks pose difficulties on the wide

use of the multimodal HRC at the controller level. The author addresses this challenge by using the concept of AFs in the collaborative assembly. A set of AFs based on the assembly logic are used to describe the assembly task, and then AF-based FBs are defined and used for assembly planning and generating robot control commands for assembly operations, which are activated by the events of AFs. In parallel, the lack of adaptive adjustment of the control parameters during assembly impacts the flexible robot motion control driven by multimodal commands. Accordingly, adaptive parameter control is adopted to adjust the position and orientation of the robot for accurate assembly operations, which is well demonstrated by the assembly case of car parts.

Finally, HRC in assembly can be categorised into different settings [23]. The author considers the collaborative scenario of an operator and a robot team. With the context, the developed multimodal interface is used for free control switch between two robots, and also the operator working in parallel with the robot team for efficient assembly is actively explored, where a group of tasks such as the quality check of the assembly and assistance work are performed by the operator as the robot team is executing assembly tasks.

7.2 Future research directions

The possible future research directions within the context of HRC are summarised from the perspectives of the author together with consideration of the limitation of the technologies and approaches presented in this thesis. It has been the authors' intention to stand on neutral ground to provide the account for HRC. It may include some opinionated comments from the authors, but it is the authors' hope that you will be in a better position to see the future directions after reading this thesis.

The future research directions are summarised as follows, and some of them are inspired by or adapted from my supervisor Professor Lihui Wang.

Brain robotics in HRC: this direction includes the following content: 1) robust and reliable signal processing approaches for brainwave feature extraction; 2) efficient machine learning algorithms for brainwave command classification with high accuracy; 3) more widespread translation of neuroscience knowledge into robotics; 4) advanced control schemes to fuse robotics and neuroscience for mutual brain-robot adaptation.

Human-centric assembly: European Commission released "Industry 5.0 – towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry", and it is supported by three pillars: human-centricity, sustainability and resilience. Human centricity means core human needs and interests are placed at the centre of the production process, aiming for a thoroughly human-centric and society-centric approach. Human-centric assembly facil-

7.2. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

itated by the four enhanced human abilities [19] of augmented robots, cognitive systems, mixed reality, and co-intelligence as well as thought-driven assistance of brain robotics would be a promising future research direction.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

This thesis studied multimodal human-robot collaboration in assembly facilitated by four control modalities associated with multimodal data. The first is to use voice instructions to control the robot motion in Cartesian space, and the algorithms are designed for voice command processing and classification, and translation of valid robot motion commands. The second is leveraging non-verbal commands (hand gesture instructions) for robot gripper control in HRC assembly, and a high-accuracy classification system is trained to identify the gesture patterns so that a hand gesture command can be associated with a valid control command of robot grippers. The third control modality is to apply brainwaves to intuitively control the industrial robots and assist collaborative assembly, especially in noisy environments with unreliable voice recognition or with the context of operators occupied with other tasks and unable to make gestures. A novel macro-micro control scheme to HRC assembly is realised by function blocks, triggered by commands from the EEG-processing deep learning system. The last is a sensorless haptic control approach to HRC assembly that allows human operators to haptically control industrial robots without using extra sensors during collaborative assembly. It offers multimodal support to HRC assembly, as an alternative to contactless commands. Next, multimodal HRC assembly is realised by leveraging multimodal data fusion for adaptive robot control and reliable collaborative assembly driven by event-driven function blocks. Along with these directions, key algorithms, system design, and experiments are investigated. Additionally, quantitative analysis of the experimental results, system performance, specific contributions and future research directions are discussed.

Bibliography

- [1] “Global robotics market - growth, trends, covid-19 impact, and forecasts (2021 - 2026),” pp. 1–173, 2021.
- [2] M. Breque, L. De Nul, and A. Petridis, “Industry 5.0 – towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient european industry,” *Luxembourg: Publications Office of European Union*, 2021.
- [3] L. Wang, R. Gao, J. Váncza, J. Krüger, X. V. Wang, S. Makris, and G. Chryssolouris, “Symbiotic human-robot collaborative assembly,” *CIRP annals*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 701–726, 2019.
- [4] E. Noohi, M. Žefran, and J. L. Patton, “A model for human–human collaborative object manipulation and its application to human–robot interaction,” *IEEE transactions on robotics*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 880–896, 2016.
- [5] S. Liu, L. Wang, and X. V. Wang, “Multimodal data driven robot control for human-robot collaborative assembly,” *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, pp. 1–15, 2022.
- [6] J. Krüger, T. K. Lien, and A. Verl, “Cooperation of human and machines in assembly lines,” *CIRP annals*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 628–646, 2009.
- [7] “Iso/ts 15066:2016 robots and robotic devices — collaborative robots,” pp. 1–33, 2016.
- [8] *Collaborative robot market size global forecast to 2027*, <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/collaborative-robot-market-194541294.html>, 2021.
- [9] *Industrial robotics market size share forecast to 2026*, <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/Industrial-Robotics-Market-643.html>, 2021.
- [10] “World robotics 2021,” *International Federation of Robotics*, pp. 1–43, 2021.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [11] W. Khalil and E. Dombre, *Modeling, Identification and Control of Robots*. 2004, pp. 1–480.
- [12] S. Liu, L. Wang, and X. V. Wang, “Sensorless haptic control for human-robot collaborative assembly,” *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, vol. 32, pp. 132–144, 2021.
- [13] S. Liu, L. Wang, X. V. Wang, C. Cooper, and R. X. Gao, “Leveraging multimodal data for intuitive robot control towards human-robot collaborative assembly,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 104, pp. 206–211, 2021.
- [14] M. Breque, L. De Nul, and A. Petridis, “Industry 5.0 – towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient european industry,” *Luxembourg: Publications Office of European Union*, pp. 1–48, 2021.
- [15] E. Matheson, R. Minto, E. G. Zampieri, M. Faccio, and G. Rosati, “Human–robot collaboration in manufacturing applications: A review,” *Robotics*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 100, 2019.
- [16] G. Michalos, S. Makris, N. Papakostas, D. Mourtzis, and G. Chrysolouris, “Automotive assembly technologies review: Challenges and outlook for a flexible and adaptive approach,” *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 81–91, 2010.
- [17] L. Wang, X. V. Wang, J. Váncza, and Z. Kemény, *Advanced Human–Robot Collaboration in Manufacturing*. Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2021, pp. 1–455.
- [18] L. Wang, S. Liu, H. Liu, and X. V. Wang, “Overview of human-robot collaboration in manufacturing,” in *Proceedings of 5th international conference on the industry 4.0 model for advanced manufacturing*, Springer, 2020, pp. 15–58.
- [19] L. Wang, “A futuristic perspective on human-centric assembly,” *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 62, pp. 199–201, 2022.
- [20] H. ElMaraghy, L. Monostori, G. Schuh, and W. ElMaraghy, “Evolution and future of manufacturing systems,” *CIRP Annals*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 635–658, 2021.
- [21] S. Hjorth and D. Chrysostomou, “Human–robot collaboration in industrial environments: A literature review on non-destructive disassembly,” *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 73, p. 102 208, 2022.
- [22] L. Pérez, S. Rodríguez-Jiménez, N. Rodríguez, R. Usamentiaga, D. F. García, and L. Wang, “Symbiotic human–robot collaborative approach for increased productivity and enhanced safety in the aerospace manufacturing industry,” *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 106, no. 3, pp. 851–863, 2020.

- [23] X. V. Wang, Z. Kemény, J. Váncza, and L. Wang, “Human–robot collaborative assembly in cyber-physical production: Classification framework and implementation,” *CIRP annals*, vol. 66, no. 1, pp. 5–8, 2017.
- [24] A. Ajoudani, A. M. Zanchettin, S. Ivaldi, A. Albu-Schäffer, K. Kotsuge, and O. Khatib, “Progress and prospects of the human–robot collaboration,” *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 957–975, 2018.
- [25] P. Tsarouchi, S. Makris, and G. Chryssolouris, “Human–robot interaction review and challenges on task planning and programming,” *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 916–931, 2016.
- [26] X. Li, Y. Pan, G. Chen, and H. Yu, “Adaptive human-robot interaction control for robots driven by series elastic actuators,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 169–182, 2016.
- [27] S. Liu, L. Wang, and X. V. Wang, “Function block-based multimodal control for symbiotic human–robot collaborative assembly,” *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, vol. 143, no. 9, 2021.
- [28] J. Arents, V. Abolins, J. Judvaitis, O. Vismanis, A. Oraby, and K. Ozols, “Human–robot collaboration trends and safety aspects: A systematic review,” *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 48, 2021.
- [29] *Human-robot collaboration: Welcome, fellow robot!* <https://www.kuka.com/en-se/future-production/human-robot-collaboration>, 2022.
- [30] *Human-robot collaboration with the abb yumi*, <https://www.robots.com/articles/human-robot-collaboration-with-the-abb-yumi>, 2022.
- [31] P. Tsarouchi, A.-S. Matthaïakis, S. Makris, and G. Chryssolouris, “On a human-robot collaboration in an assembly cell,” *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 580–589, 2017.
- [32] G. Adamson, L. Wang, and P. Moore, “Feature-based control and information framework for adaptive and distributed manufacturing in cyber physical systems,” *Journal of manufacturing systems*, vol. 43, pp. 305–315, 2017.
- [33] L. Wang, B. Schmidt, M. Givehchi, and G. Adamson, “Robotic assembly planning and control with enhanced adaptability through function blocks,” *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 77, no. 1, pp. 705–715, 2015.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [34] C. Kardos, A. Kovács, and J. Váncza, “Decomposition approach to optimal feature-based assembly planning,” *CIRP Annals*, vol. 66, no. 1, pp. 417–420, 2017.
- [35] V. Villani, F. Pini, F. Leali, and C. Secchi, “Survey on human–robot collaboration in industrial settings: Safety, intuitive interfaces and applications,” *Mechatronics*, vol. 55, pp. 248–266, 2018.
- [36] I. Maurtua, A. Ibarguren, J. Kildal, L. Susperregi, and B. Sierra, “Human–robot collaboration in industrial applications: Safety, interaction and trust,” *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 1729881417716010, 2017.
- [37] A. M. Zanchettin, N. M. Ceriani, P. Rocco, H. Ding, and B. Matthias, “Safety in human-robot collaborative manufacturing environments: Metrics and control,” *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 882–893, 2015.
- [38] G. Michalos, S. Makris, P. Tsarouchi, T. Guasch, D. Kontovrakis, and G. Chryssolouris, “Design considerations for safe human-robot collaborative workplaces,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 37, pp. 248–253, 2015.
- [39] “Iso/tr 23482-1:2020 - robotics — application of iso 13482,” pp. 1–79, 2020.
- [40] G. Michalos, N. Kousi, P. Karagiannis, C. Gkournelos, K. Dimoulas, S. Koukas, K. Mparis, A. Papavasileiou, and S. Makris, “Seamless human robot collaborative assembly—an automotive case study,” *Mechatronics*, vol. 55, pp. 194–211, 2018.
- [41] A. Cherubini, R. Passama, A. Crosnier, A. Lasnier, and P. Fraise, “Collaborative manufacturing with physical human–robot interaction,” *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 40, pp. 1–13, 2016.
- [42] W. Wang, R. Li, Y. Chen, Z. M. Diekel, and Y. Jia, “Facilitating human–robot collaborative tasks by teaching-learning-collaboration from human demonstrations,” *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 640–653, 2018.
- [43] L. Wang, S. Liu, C. Cooper, X. V. Wang, and R. X. Gao, “Function block-based human-robot collaborative assembly driven by brain-waves,” *CIRP annals*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 5–8, 2021.
- [44] S. Iba, C. J. Paredis, and P. K. Khosla, “Interactive multimodal robot programming,” *The international journal of robotics research*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 83–104, 2005.

- [45] K. Lin, Y. Li, J. Sun, D. Zhou, and Q. Zhang, “Multi-sensor fusion for body sensor network in medical human–robot interaction scenario,” *Information Fusion*, vol. 57, pp. 15–26, 2020.
- [46] T. Xue, W. Wang, J. Ma, W. Liu, Z. Pan, and M. Han, “Progress and prospects of multimodal fusion methods in physical human–robot interaction: A review,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 20, no. 18, pp. 10 355–10 370, 2020.
- [47] P. Wang, Z. Fan, D. O. Kazmer, and R. X. Gao, “Orthogonal analysis of multisensor data fusion for improved quality control,” *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, vol. 139, no. 10, pp. 101008-1–8, 2017.
- [48] S. Makris, P. Tsarouchi, D. Surdilovic, and J. Krüger, “Intuitive dual arm robot programming for assembly operations,” *CIRP Annals*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 13–16, 2014.
- [49] H. Liu, T. Fang, T. Zhou, Y. Wang, and L. Wang, “Deep learning-based multimodal control interface for human-robot collaboration,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 72, pp. 3–8, 2018.
- [50] O. Rogalla, M. Ehrenmann, R. Zollner, R. Becher, and R. Dillmann, “Using gesture and speech control for commanding a robot assistant,” in *IEEE International Workshop on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*, Citeseer, 2002, pp. 454–459.
- [51] A. Albu-Schaffer and G. Hirzinger, “Cartesian impedance control techniques for torque controlled light-weight robots,” in *Proceedings 2002 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (Cat. No. 02CH37292)*, IEEE, vol. 1, 2002, pp. 657–663.
- [52] G. Grunwald, G. Schreiber, A. Albu-Schaffer, and G. Hirzinger, “Touch: The direct type of human interaction with a redundant service robot,” in *Proceedings 10th IEEE International Workshop on Robot and Human Interactive Communication. ROMAN 2001 (Cat. No. 01TH8591)*, IEEE, 2001, pp. 347–352.
- [53] D. Perzanowski, A. C. Schultz, W. Adams, E. Marsh, and M. Bugajska, “Building a multimodal human-robot interface,” *IEEE intelligent systems*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 16–21, 2001.
- [54] P. Neto, J. N. Pires, and A. P. Moreira, “High-level programming and control for industrial robotics: Using a hand-held accelerometer-based input device for gesture and posture recognition,” *Industrial Robot: An International Journal*, 2010.
- [55] P. Gustavsson, A. Syberfeldt, R. Brewster, and L. Wang, “Human-robot collaboration demonstrator combining speech recognition and haptic control,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 63, pp. 396–401, 2017.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [56] *Eu project: Symbio-tic*, <http://www.symbio-tic.eu/>, 2019.
- [57] C. Kardos, Z. Kemény, A. Kovács, B. E. Pataki, and J. Váncza, “Context-dependent multimodal communication in human-robot collaboration,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 72, pp. 15–20, 2018.
- [58] M. J. Islam, M. Ho, and J. Sattar, “Understanding human motion and gestures for underwater human–robot collaboration,” *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 851–873, 2019.
- [59] H. Liu and L. Wang, “Gesture recognition for human-robot collaboration: A review,” *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, vol. 68, pp. 355–367, 2018.
- [60] V. I. Pavlovic, R. Sharma, and T. S. Huang, “Visual interpretation of hand gestures for human-computer interaction: A review,” *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, vol. 19, no. 7, pp. 677–695, 1997.
- [61] P. Wang, H. Liu, L. Wang, and R. X. Gao, “Deep learning-based human motion recognition for predictive context-aware human-robot collaboration,” *CIRP annals*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 17–20, 2018.
- [62] G. Cheng, S. K. Ehrlich, M. Lebedev, and M. A. Nicolelis, “Neuro-engineering challenges of fusing robotics and neuroscience,” *Science Robotics*, vol. 5, no. 49, eabd1911, 2020.
- [63] M. A. Lebedev and M. A. Nicolelis, “Brain-machine interfaces: From basic science to neuroprostheses and neurorehabilitation,” *Physiological reviews*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 767–837, 2017.
- [64] B. He, H. Yuan, J. Meng, and S. Gao, “Brain–computer interfaces,” in *Neural engineering*, Springer, 2020, pp. 131–183.
- [65] A. Kawala-Sterniuk, N. Browarska, A. Al-Bakri, M. Pelc, J. Zygarlicki, M. Sidikova, R. Martinek, and E. J. Gorzelanczyk, “Summary of over fifty years with brain-computer interfaces—a review,” *Brain Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 43, 2021.
- [66] T. Radüntz, “Signal quality evaluation of emerging eeg devices,” *Frontiers in physiology*, vol. 9, p. 98, 2018.
- [67] A. Vourvopoulos and F. Liarokapis, “Evaluation of commercial brain–computer interfaces in real and virtual world environment: A pilot study,” *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 714–729, 2014.
- [68] X. Tang, W. Li, X. Li, W. Ma, and X. Dang, “Motor imagery eeg recognition based on conditional optimization empirical mode decomposition and multi-scale convolutional neural network,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 149, p. 113285, 2020.

- [69] M. Aljalal, S. Ibrahim, R. Djemal, and W. Ko, “Comprehensive review on brain-controlled mobile robots and robotic arms based on electroencephalography signals,” *Intelligent Service Robotics*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 539–563, 2020.
- [70] P. Boonyakitanont, A. Lek-Uthai, K. Chomtho, and J. Songsiri, “A review of feature extraction and performance evaluation in epileptic seizure detection using eeg,” *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 57, p. 101702, 2020.
- [71] A. Craik, Y. He, and J. L. Contreras-Vidal, “Deep learning for electroencephalogram (eeg) classification tasks: A review,” *Journal of neural engineering*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 031001, 2019.
- [72] Y. Roy, H. Banville, I. Albuquerque, A. Gramfort, T. H. Falk, and J. Faubert, “Deep learning-based electroencephalography analysis: A systematic review,” *Journal of neural engineering*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 051001, 2019.
- [73] A. Al-Saegh, S. A. Dawwd, and J. M. Abdul-Jabbar, “Deep learning for motor imagery eeg-based classification: A review,” *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 63, p. 102172, 2021.
- [74] M. Hägele, K. Nilsson, J. N. Pires, and R. Bischoff, “Industrial robotics,” in *Springer handbook of robotics*, Springer, 2016, pp. 1385–1422.
- [75] K. Kokkalis, G. Michalos, P. Aivaliotis, and S. Makris, “An approach for implementing power and force limiting in sensorless industrial robots,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 76, pp. 138–143, 2018.
- [76] S. Liu, L. Wang, and X. V. Wang, “Symbiotic human-robot collaboration: Multimodal control using function blocks,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 93, pp. 1188–1193, 2020.
- [77] G. Sebastian, Z. Li, V. Crocher, D. Kremers, Y. Tan, and D. Oetomo, “Interaction Force Estimation Using Extended State Observers: An Application to Impedance-Based Assistive and Rehabilitation Robotics,” *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1156–1161, 2019.
- [78] M. Ragaglia, A. M. Zanchettin, L. Bascetta, and P. Rocco, “Accurate sensorless lead-through programming for lightweight robots in structured environments,” *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 39, pp. 9–21, 2016.
- [79] W. H. Chen, J. Yang, L. Guo, and S. Li, “Disturbance-Observer-Based Control and Related Methods - An Overview,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 1083–1095, 2016.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [80] M. J. Kim and W. K. Chung, “Disturbance-observer-based pd control of flexible joint robots for asymptotic convergence,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 1508–1516, 2015.
- [81] A. Wahrburg, J. Bös, K. D. Listmann, F. Dai, B. Matthias, and H. Ding, “Motor-current-based estimation of cartesian contact forces and torques for robotic manipulators and its application to force control,” *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 879–886, 2017.
- [82] E. Abele, M. Weigold, and S. Rothenbücher, “Modeling and identification of an industrial robot for machining applications,” *CIRP annals*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 387–390, 2007.
- [83] W. Khalil and E. Dombre, *Modeling identification and control of robots*. CRC Press, 2002.
- [84] N. Mallon, N. van de Wouw, D. Putra, and H. Nijmeijer, “Friction compensation in a controlled one-link robot using a reduced-order observer,” *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 374–383, 2006.
- [85] B. Bona and M. Indri, “Friction compensation in robotics: An overview,” in *Proceedings of the 44th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, IEEE, 2005, pp. 4360–4367.
- [86] J. Swevers, F. Al-Bender, C. G. Ganseman, and T. Projogo, “An integrated friction model structure with improved presliding behavior for accurate friction compensation,” *IEEE Transactions on automatic control*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 675–686, 2000.
- [87] V. Lampaert, J. Swevers, and F. Al-Bender, “Modification of the leuven integrated friction model structure,” *IEEE transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 683–687, 2002.
- [88] F. Al-Bender, V. Lampaert, and J. Swevers, “The generalized maxwell-slip model: A novel model for friction simulation and compensation,” *IEEE Transactions on automatic control*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 1883–1887, 2005.
- [89] Y. Hu, H. Su, L. Zhang, S. Miao, G. Chen, and A. Knoll, “Nonlinear model predictive control for mobile robot using varying-parameter convergent differential neural network,” *Robotics*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 64, 2019.
- [90] L. Zhang, Z. Li, Y. Hu, C. Smith, E. M. G. Farewik, and R. Wang, “Ankle joint torque estimation using an emg-driven neuromusculoskeletal model and an artificial neural network model,” *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering*, 2020.

- [91] K. Guo, Y. Pan, and H. Yu, “Composite learning robot control with friction compensation: A neural network-based approach,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 10, pp. 7841–7851, 2018.
- [92] S. Huang, W. Liang, and K. K. Tan, “Intelligent Friction Compensation: A Review,” *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, pp. 1–1, 2019.
- [93] N. Hirose and R. Tajima, “Modeling of rolling friction by recurrent neural network using lstm,” in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, IEEE, 2017, pp. 6471–6478.
- [94] C. Ott, R. Mukherjee, and Y. Nakamura, “Unified impedance and admittance control,” in *2010 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation*, IEEE, 2010, pp. 554–561.
- [95] A. Q. Keemink, H. van der Kooij, and A. H. Stienen, “Admittance control for physical human–robot interaction,” *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 1421–1444, 2018.
- [96] S. Papanastasiou, N. Kousi, P. Karagiannis, C. Gkournelos, A. Pappavasileiou, K. Dimoulas, K. Baris, S. Koukas, G. Michalos, and S. Makris, “Towards seamless human robot collaboration: Integrating multimodal interaction,” *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 105, no. 9, pp. 3881–3897, 2019.
- [97] D. Kent, C. Saldanha, and S. Chernova, “Leveraging depth data in remote robot teleoperation interfaces for general object manipulation,” *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 39–53, 2020.
- [98] C. Pohlt, T. Schlegl, and S. Wachsmuth, “Weakly-supervised learning for multimodal human activity recognition in human-robot collaboration scenarios,” in *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, IEEE, 2020, pp. 8381–8386.
- [99] S. K. Ande, M. R. Kuchibotla, and B. K. Adavi, “Robot acquisition, control and interfacing using multimodal feedback,” *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 3909–3919, 2021.
- [100] “International electrotechnical commission, 2005. international standard of function blocks – part 1: Architecture, iec 61499,” pp. 1–111, 2005.
- [101] W. Fan, L. Zheng, W. Ji, X. Xu, L. Wang, Y. Lu, and X. Zhao, “Function block-based closed-loop adaptive machining for assembly interfaces of large-scale aircraft components,” *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 66, p. 101994, 2020.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [102] K. Thramboulidis, “Comments on “bridging service-oriented architecture and iec 61499 for flexibility and interoperability”,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 1494–1496, 2016.
- [103] V. Vyatkin and I. S. of America, “Iec 61499 function blocks for embedded and distributed control systems design,” 2007.
- [104] L. Wang and A. Haghghi, “Combined strength of holons, agents and function blocks in cyber-physical systems,” *Journal of manufacturing systems*, vol. 40, pp. 25–34, 2016.
- [105] V. Vyatkin, “Iec 61499 as enabler of distributed and intelligent automation: State-of-the-art review,” . *IEEE transactions on Industrial Informatics*. 2011 Sep 19;7(4):768-81., vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 768–781, 2011.
- [106] N. Tapoglou, J. Mehnen, A. Vlachou, M. Doukas, N. Milas, and D. Mourtzis, “Cloud-based platform for optimal machining parameter selection based on function blocks and real-time monitoring,” *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, vol. 137, no. 4, pp. 040909-1–11, 2015.
- [107] L. Wang, G. Adamson, M. Holm, and P. Moore, “A review of function blocks for process planning and control of manufacturing equipment,” *Journal of manufacturing systems*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 269–279, 2012.
- [108] L. Wang, S. Keshavarzmanesh, and H.-Y. Feng, “Design of adaptive function blocks for dynamic assembly planning and control,” *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 45–51, 2008.
- [109] T. Strasser, M. Rooker, G. Ebenhofer, A. Zoitl, C. Sunder, A. Valentini, and A. Martel, “Framework for distributed industrial automation and control (4diac),” in *2008 6th IEEE international conference on industrial informatics*, IEEE, 2008, pp. 283–288.
- [110] *4diac ide – iec 61499 compliant development environment*, https://www.eclipse.org/4diac/en_ide.php.
- [111] *4diac forte – iec 61499 runtime environment*, https://www.eclipse.org/4diac/en_rte.php.
- [112] *4diac lib – iec 61499 function block library*, https://www.eclipse.org/4diac/en_lib.php.
- [113] M.-P. Hosseini, A. Hosseini, and K. Ahi, “A review on machine learning for eeg signal processing in bioengineering,” *IEEE reviews in biomedical engineering*, vol. 14, pp. 204–218, 2020.

- [114] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, “Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 25, 2012.
- [115] Y. Yu, X. Si, C. Hu, and J. Zhang, “A review of recurrent neural networks: Lstm cells and network architectures,” *Neural computation*, vol. 31, no. 7, pp. 1235–1270, 2019.
- [116] C.-H. Lin and S. Lucey, “Inverse compositional spatial transformer networks,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2017, pp. 2568–2576.
- [117] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, “Long short-term memory,” *Neural computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.
- [118] R. Dey and F. M. Salem, “Gate-variants of gated recurrent unit (gru) neural networks,” in *2017 IEEE 60th international midwest symposium on circuits and systems (MWSCAS)*, IEEE, 2017, pp. 1597–1600.
- [119] J. Li, R. Zhao, H. Hu, and Y. Gong, “Improving rnn transducer modeling for end-to-end speech recognition,” in *2019 IEEE Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding Workshop (ASRU)*, IEEE, 2019, pp. 114–121.
- [120] K. Zhang, W. Zuo, Y. Chen, D. Meng, and L. Zhang, “Beyond a gaussian denoiser: Residual learning of deep cnn for image denoising,” *IEEE transactions on image processing*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 3142–3155, 2017.
- [121] K. Chen, J. Wang, L.-C. Chen, H. Gao, W. Xu, and R. Nevatia, “Abc-cnn: An attention based convolutional neural network for visual question answering,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.05960*, 2015.
- [122] P. Neto, D. Pereira, J. N. Pires, and A. P. Moreira, “Real-time and continuous hand gesture spotting: An approach based on artificial neural networks,” in *2013 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation*, IEEE, 2013, pp. 178–183.
- [123] P. Wang, A. Jiang, X. Liu, J. Shang, and L. Zhang, “Lstm-based eeg classification in motor imagery tasks,” *IEEE transactions on neural systems and rehabilitation engineering*, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 2086–2095, 2018.
- [124] S. Zhang, H. Tong, J. Xu, and R. Maciejewski, “Graph convolutional networks: A comprehensive review,” *Computational Social Networks*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–23, 2019.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [125] Z. Wu, S. Pan, F. Chen, G. Long, C. Zhang, and S. Y. Philip, “A comprehensive survey on graph neural networks,” *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 4–24, 2020.
- [126] J. de Gea Fernández, D. Mronga, M. Günther, T. Knobloch, M. Wirkus, M. Schröer, M. Trampler, S. Stiene, E. Kirchner, V. Bargsten, *et al.*, “Multimodal sensor-based whole-body control for human-robot collaboration in industrial settings,” *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 94, pp. 102–119, 2017.
- [127] Q. Lv, R. Zhang, X. Sun, Y. Lu, and J. Bao, “A digital twin-driven human-robot collaborative assembly approach in the wake of covid-19,” *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 60, pp. 837–851, 2021.
- [128] C. Kardos, A. Kovács, and J. Váncza, “A constraint model for assembly planning,” *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 54, pp. 196–203, 2020.
- [129] P. Warden, “Speech commands: A dataset for limited-vocabulary speech recognition,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.03209*, 2018.
- [130] R. X. Gao and R. Yan, *Wavelets: Theory and applications for manufacturing*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [131] B. Yu, H. Yin, and Z. Zhu, “Spatio-temporal graph convolutional networks: A deep learning framework for traffic forecasting,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1709.04875*, 2017.
- [132] K. K. Thekumparampil, C. Wang, S. Oh, and L.-J. Li, “Attention-based graph neural network for semi-supervised learning,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1803.03735*, 2018.
- [133] H. Wang, L. Xu, A. Bezerianos, C. Chen, and Z. Zhang, “Linking attention-based multiscale cnn with dynamical gcn for driving fatigue detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 70, pp. 1–11, 2020.
- [134] *Kuka. system software*, [online]. available: https://www.kuka.com/en-se/products/robotics-systems/software/system-software/kuka{_}systemsoftware.
- [135] F. Sanfilippo, L. I. Hatledal, H. Zhang, M. Fago, and K. Y. Pettersen, “Controlling kuka industrial robots: Flexible communication interface jopenshowvar,” *IEEE robotics & automation magazine*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 96–109, 2015.